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Personal authentication using verified electronic document

Abstract:

In the modern world, there are quite a large number of various documents that certify (both independently of each other and in aggregate) both the identity of the owner and his social and legal rights and opportunities. However, there are several problems in this field. The paper dwells on the research of the possibility of bringing personal identification documents to a digital format with guaranteed person authentication and verification of the document, based on the digitalization trends of modern society and the increasing capabilities of technical support to eliminate the likelihood of damage, falsification and other negative impacts on the existing document flow. The main problem in solving this problem is the choice of the most effective type of used biometric parameters of a person for reading, broadcasting and subsequent processing.

Keywords:

authentication, electronic document management, digitalization, personal identification, biometric parameters.

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Персональная аутентификация с использованием верифицируемого электронного документа

Аннотация:

В современном мире существует довольно большое количество различных документов, которые удостоверяют (как независимо друг от друга, так и в совокупности) как личность владельца, так и его социальные и юридические права и возможности. Однако в этой области существует несколько проблем. В статье подробно рассматривается исследование возможности перевода документов, удостоверяющих личность, в цифровой формат с

гарантированной аутентификацией личности и верификацией документа, исходя из тенденций цифровизации современного общества и возрастающих возможностей технической поддержки по устранению вероятности порчи, фальсификации и других негативных воздействий на существующий документооборот. Основной проблемой при решении этой задачи является выбор наиболее эффективного типа используемых биометрических параметров человека для считывания, трансляции и последующей обработки.

Ключевые слова:

аутентификация, электронный документооборот, оцифровка, идентификация личности, биометрические параметры.

Introduction

In the modern world, there are quite a large number of various documents that certify (both independently of each other and in aggregate) both the identity of the owner and his social and legal rights and opportunities. However, there are several problems in this field:

- most of the documents are in the paper version, which significantly reduces the wear resistance and durability;
- an existing document can be verified for authenticity and established compliance with the identity using special tools and access to a single database, which significantly affects the speed and ability to verify, e.g., if there is no technical possibility of communication with the database;
- user authentication occurs by photo, which leads to possible errors (when changing appearance, with age changes, relatives, doubles);
- constant changes of documents (when reaching the age, changing data, adding new functions), so stored information, related to the user, grows exponentially during the life of the person;
- due to the high growth rates of innovative and digital technologies, it is necessary fully to replace current documents with electronic ones without loss of originality and security;
- due to the growing mobility of citizens, as well as to ensure the constant possibility of identity authentication, the transition to multi-copy (without loss of originality and authenticity) electronic documents is a necessity, dictated by the rhythm and quality of life and the increasing amount of information in the world requiring a certain systematization, protection, and proper storage and display with the function of a quick search of needed information.

To date, the first attempts have already been made to switch to electronic documents for citizens, but encryption methods using personal characteristics of a person are not applied for their use and security. One of these developments is the *Electronic Passport of a Citizen of the Russian Federation*. The project is a plastic card with a chip sized a bank card. In addition to the usual passport data, fingerprints, iris pattern and other biometric authentication data, driver's license data, migration registration data, *INILA* (Insurance Number of the Individual Ledger Account), *ITN* (Individual Taxpayer Number), as well as an electronic signature can be recorded on it (Electronic passport of a citizen of the Russian Federation), which is an intermediate stage between the transition to a fully electronic document format from paper media and the reduction of stored databases by reducing the number of documents.

The first association when discussing identity authentication using electronic documents and/or technical means is the use of biometric parameters, and this is really the simplest (in terms of the availability of parameters) and logical way to identify a person. However, when considering in detail the possible types of biometric parameters, their reading and analysis, we can conclude that this task is not so elementary even at the stage of selecting parameters without taking into account the second part of the task, namely, the use of a verified electronic document to authenticate. So, this task is automatically divided into two subtasks:

- determining the type of biometric parameters;
- a verified electronic document containing the information necessary for identity authentication.

To solve these main problems, it is proposed to assume that there is an abstract universal system to read, analyze and process biometric parameters (and information about them in an electronic document) of any type.

We should consider the first part of the problem, namely: choosing the type of biometric parameters. The most common currently (and the oldest way: the hypothesis of the immutability of the papillary pattern of the palmar surfaces of human skin was put forward by William Herschel in 1877 and was first used to identify a criminal in the UK in 1902) is fingerprinting, otherwise, scanning fingerprints, to be more precise, the capillary pattern of the fingertips. At the moment, 100% uniqueness of each individual's fingerprints is not clearly defined, and this statement is based only on practical data (Kukharev, 2001). Practice shows that the fingerprints of different people may have the same global characteristics, but

there are no identical micro-nodes. Therefore, global characteristics are used to divide the database into classes at the authentication stage. At the second stage of recognition, local features are already used. Upon detailed examination, it turns out that the results can be significantly distorted with a certain reading error (depending on the quality of equipment, surface cleanliness, finger cleanliness, the presence and absence of skin damage, the position of the finger on the scanner) and the use of this method in electronic document management can bring more difficulties than simplifications and optimization of the process for both the identified person and the body identifying this person. Fingerprint conformity assessment is performed using the formula:

$$K = \frac{D^2}{p * q} * 100$$

D – the number of matched minutiae (local patterns),

p – the number of standard minutiae,

q – the number of identifiable fingerprint minutiae.

If the result exceeds 65%, the prints are considered identical (the threshold can be changed when setting other accuracy parameters) (Dactyloscopy).

The second most popular parameter is the iris. The first discoveries in this field were made in the late 1930s. In 1936, American eye surgeon Frank Bursch was the first, who thought that the human eye and its iris can be used for personality recognition, and his idea was patented by Leonard Flom and Aran Safir in 1987. In 1989, they turned to John Daugman to develop recognition theory and algorithms. It is John Daugman who is considered to be the founder of this method of biometric authentication. Today the authentication technology using iris scanning is gaining popularity and is one of the leading information security technologies on the market (Iris authentication). The process of recognizing a person using the iris can be divided into three stages: digital image acquisition, segmentation, and parameterization. The image for analysis is made in high quality. For this purpose, a monochrome *CCD-camera* with dim illumination is used, which is sensitive to infrared radiation. After defining the borders, the iris image must be normalized. After normalization using pseudo-polar coordinates, the selected area of the image becomes a rectangle, and the radius and centre of the iris are estimated (Dmitriev et al., 2016). The iris of the eye is considered one of the most convenient to be scanned and one of the most constant parameters during a person's life, but it can change quite significantly with severe injuries and surgical intervention.

Another of the most commonly used and easy-to-process parameters is the human voice. This method is currently widely used in banking and other structures with the possibility of voice calling. There are a sufficient number of ways to define parameters for voice identification, as well as to store data for processing and comparison with the stored template. However, in cases of colds, allergies, and other diseases that cause voice signal distortion, this system has a high risk of access failure, which significantly affects the quality of identification availability and the tasks outlined above (Gavrilova & Taran, 2020).

The different distribution of blood vessels in the retina of the eye has a structure that is unique to each individual, so it can be used as a means of confirming the identity and is the most reasoned for the purposes set out in this paper. Thanks to the work of Dr P. Tower, it was found that even in twins, the structure of the retina is different (Kukharev, 2001). The retina does not change much during a person's lifetime, except in cases of illness or blindness. In terms of scanning complexity, the retina slightly exceeds the iris but, in terms of usability of the data, obtained during scanning, the retina is the most preferable due to the possibility of a coordinate method for selecting the scanning area, the amount of information stored and evaluated, and the number of unique parameters and characteristics for comparison and identification (Authentication via the retina of the eye). Research by the US national laboratory showed that the probability of a second-type error with this authentication method is extremely low (less than 1%). Based on the analysis provided, the most preferred type of biometric parameters for identity authentication is retinal scanning.

To solve the second part of the problem, namely, determining the verified document for identity authentication, it is necessary to determine:

- parameters, which this document should have,
- the method of storing and verifying this document,
- the type of information for identity authentication.

The document identifying the bearer's identity must have comprehensive but not over-saturated data about the person. At the moment, such data is the last name, first name, patronymic (if it is), date of birth and a unique number assigned to a document (not a person) that certifies the identity and when issuing a new document (or a new type of document, such as a driver's license), a new number is assigned, so in turn, this leads to progressive amounts of stored information about each identified person. When switching to electronic document management, it is advisable to replace all existing identifiers (document numbers) with a single unique number

assigned to a person but not to a specific document. For this reason, the universal data set (passport, driver's license, *INIL4*, policy, etc.), in turn, must and should be replaced by a single electronic document with the social and legal characteristics of a particular person (identified person) registered and fully integrated into a common database. This system will allow us to store simultaneously all relevant information in a single 'file', prevent the reproduction of various forms and the number of documents (and their identifying numbers that need to be stored later) increasing the risk of loss and distortion. Also, this system will provide ease of use and comfort both for the user and for various government, and other interested structures, due to the possibility to use outside the stable communication zones without carrying additional devices and forms (for the user), a high degree of reliability and speed ensuring minimal failures for the first and second types of errors.

The method of storing an electronic document must not only be reliable but also convenient for the person himself allowing to present and use the document at any time and in any conditions, even if there is no electronic device. This postulate leads to an understanding of the need to create a multi-copy protected document that can be stored not only on the original physical media but also in the cloud space with conditionally open access. This storage method imposes additional restrictions and increases the necessary degree of document protection to avoid the possibility of distortion, loss, availability, and falsification of the document.

To authenticate an individual using the proposed format of an electronic document, it is necessary to put an area in the document itself that stores information about the biometric parameters of the individual. The most correct approach, in this case, is a distributed point record of data in the entire volume of an electronic document, the storage coordinates of which will be determined using a unique encryption algorithm determined and calculated from scanned biometric data, thereby reducing the likelihood of errors when reading the document, data falsification, and the possibility of dynamic changes in the document itself and the variability of its use. Thus, biometric parameters will be not only an authentication system, storage method, and document coordinate plane but also a key for data decryption making the system as autonomous, independent, and secure as possible, accessible to identity authentication at any time without the cost of storing and accessing the person database, which in large cities and countries significantly reduces the load and saves both time and material resources not only in the short term, but also in the long term, when the system is constantly used, due to the absence of the need to re-issue any printed or other verified documents, the issuance of several types of documents per person, and the reduction of interdepartmental queries and

data flows due to the availability of complete information about the person in one ‘file’.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that the proposed system, in contrast to existing solutions, makes it possible

- to simplify and reduce both the use of identifying documents and their number, reduce the risks of erroneous acceptance of documents, incorrect processing of citizens’ applications, and then avoid pre-trial and judicial proceedings in connection with incorrect data or their processing, including falsification;
- to reduce the cost of producing and printing standard types of documents on paper and other physical media in a special secure way, re-issuing and printing them if they lose or lose their readable form;
- to reduce the number of documents used to one per person;
- to implement a comfortable environment for using documents for their owners.

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Model of a document protection algorithm for a person based on biometric parameters

Abstract:

At the moment, various types of paper documents, which carry various social and legal values relative to the citizen presenting them (passport, driver's license, etc.), are used to identify a person. In the field of electronic document management, electronic digital signatures have been created and implemented to transmit the generated document packages using network technologies. This paper discusses the principle of an algorithm for protecting an identifying document using biometric data without using third-party servers for both storing and processing information. The entire operation of the system is focused on the transition from paper documents to the electronic (cloud) version without loss of uniqueness and security with the possibility of multi-copying and use outside the work of data transmission networks.

Keywords:

authentication, electronic document management, verification, personal identification, biometric parameters, personal data.

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Модель алгоритма защиты персональных документов на основе биометрических параметров

Аннотация:

В настоящее время для идентификации личности используются различные виды бумажных документов, которые несут различные социальные и правовые ценности по отношению к гражданину, их предъявляющему (паспорт, водительские права и т.д.). В области электронного документооборота были созданы и внедрены электронные цифровые

подписи для передачи сгенерированных пакетов документов с использованием сетевых технологий. В статье рассматривается принцип алгоритма защиты идентифицирующего документа с использованием биометрических данных без использования сторонних серверов как для хранения, так и для обработки информации. Вся работа системы ориентирована на переход от бумажных документов к электронному (облачному) варианту без потери уникальности и безопасности с возможностью многократного копирования и использования передачи данных вне работы сетей.

Ключевые слова:

аутентификация, электронный документооборот, верификация, идентификация личности, биометрические параметры, персональные данные.

Introduction

At the moment, various types of paper documents, which carry various social and legal values relative to the citizen presenting them (passport, driver's license, etc.), are used to identify a person. In the field of electronic document management, electronic digital signatures have been created and implemented to transmit the generated document packages using network technologies.

Currently, many public and private services have started to use modern methods of paperless processing and exchange of documents, which can significantly reduce the time spent on processing documents, transactions and their exchange, as well as improve and reduce the cost of preparing, delivering, recording and storing them. Digital signature for individuals is a way to speed up and simplify interaction with government agencies, employers, etc.

At the same time, when switching to electronic document management, important questions, i.e., the question of the authorship of the document, and, no less important, the question of its authenticity and protection from changes, arise. The most convenient means of protecting electronic documents from distortion, while allowing uniquely to identify the sender of the message, is an electronic digital signature. The external expression of an electronic signature has nothing in common with a handwritten signature, but the purpose of both types of signatures is the same: document authentication (Khachaturova, 2016).

Based on the described purpose, an electronic digital signature does not allow to identify a person, which poses a new task to switch to an electronic document format that allows uniquely to identify a person with the possibility of universal use with a full set of parameters that reduce the number of documents used by a person to one without losing the functionality and originality of the document.

To solve the problem of switching to a full-fledged electronic document flow in the field of identification and authentication of an individual, it is necessary not only to determine the initial parameters, the use of which will uniquely identify the person, the kind and type of electronic document and the method of its storage but also to determine the method of cryptographic protection of this document using the basic principles and theoretical basis of this document flow.

To authenticate an individual using an electronic document, it is necessary to include an area in the document that stores information about the biometric parameters of the individual. This article considers a distributed point record of data in the entire volume of an electronic document, the storage coordinates of which will be determined using a unique encryption algorithm determined and calculated from scanned biometric data, thereby reducing the probability of errors when reading the document, data falsification, and the possibility of dynamic changes in the document itself and the variability of its use (Bokareva, 2020).

Nowadays, the interest of specialists in the field of information security, in particular, protection of electronic documents from forgery, focuses on the development of cryptography methods based on the use of deterministic-chaotic processes more and more often (Dovgalet al. 2004; Dovgal & Zacharov, 2008). This class of processes is characterized by instability, which results in non-repeatability of the values of elements in a sequence of numbers with a representative bit grid. So-called nonlinear mappings depending on their dimensionality are used as generators of chaotic deterministic processes. For example, the values of all variables (twos, threes, etc.) are not repeated in two-dimensional and three-dimensional maps (Parker & Zhua, 1987; Thompson, 1985).

If the initial display values are unknown, the attacker must perform a complete search of all irrational numbers, as well as all numbers obtained using the generators of deterministic-chaotic process, which significantly increases the cryptographic strength of the proposed methods (Gordienko et al., 2018).

Currently, there is an active introduction and use of electronic digital signatures to transfer documents between various public and private entities. When signing electronic documents, a digital signature ensures authenticity, i.e., makes it possible to check the document for integrity and originality. Integrity, in turn, consists of the fact that the content of information in the document cannot be modified by an unauthorized user. The signature is generated by a cryptographic operation, for which the document and private key are presented. This key should only be known to the person signing the document. To verify the document, a public (test) key,

which can be known to everyone, is used. Nobody can get a private key from this public key. A test, in turn, is a cryptographic operation, for which a document and a test key are provided (Bakhimova et al., 2016).

These methods are widely used, and the stability of the algorithms has been proven both theoretically and over the entire period of use. However, these algorithms are not applicable for solving the tasks due to some factors: the need for fully autonomous operation of the system (which eliminates the possibility of any outside resources), cloud storage of document and the requirement of unambiguous identification.

Using biometric parameters as both a key and a method of cryptographic protection is the best option to solve this problem. If the read biometric data are presented in the form of a coordinate grid, then the process of document verification and identity authentication can be organized through a predefined function for changing the characteristics (digital code) of a point, defined by the coordinate grid of biometric parameters (hereinafter – the change map). Accordingly, when reading biometric parameters, we get:

- a map of changes (coordinates of points that need to be modified for verification and authentication),
- a key to the point change algorithm,
- a low probability of failures of the 1st and 2nd types.

Due to the absence of the need to request and transfer any data to other devices and servers, the system is completely autonomous and allows to reduce the time and cost of using it, which in some cases is extremely important.

Although the retinal identification algorithm was proposed, developed and proved to be unique for each person, its use in practice was significantly difficult due to the high (until recently) cost of the necessary equipment and special scanning conditions, which could give erroneous data with a reading error. However, with the development of technology, especially in the field of mobile devices in terms of technical parameters and the expansion of mobile applications, retinal scanning has moved to a new level and is available to be used almost everyone, who has a smartphone at their disposal. Naturally, applications and technical capabilities affect the quality and level of detail of the scanned image (data), and the use of the simplest applications, which are available to each user, does not provide the ability to operate with the necessary amount of data to identify a person in the framework of the task but provides prerequisites for the development of less expensive devices and software for full-fledged scanning of biometric parameters of a person to organize

subsequent work with the read data in the framework of the task.

The proposed algorithm for data encryption in an electronic identification document can be schematically represented as an interacting system consisting of three matrices and a method (relationship) for data modification (transformation) when writing or reading them from the final file. The first matrix represents the original data of the person that has to be saved in an electronic document in a secure form. The second matrix is a map of changes (read biometric data of a person, converted into the necessary form for work). The third matrix is the file itself, in which the changed points (data) from the first matrix will be 'appended' using data from the second matrix (namely, the coordinates of the change, the change itself, and the encryption method).

When decrypting data from a file containing an electronic document, the use of biometric data other than the original data of the identified person will lead to erroneous (not readable by humans) data, which in turn will make it impossible to identify the person under other documents, since significant data is read from the map of changes (agreed with it) – the formation of the original document file will be impossible without distortion and loss.

To create the first matrix, data from the scanned retina of the eye is used. This article considers reading the intersections of blood vessels located on the retina. Before starting the scan, a specialist needs to determine whether the eye is alive. When tracking the movement of the eyeball, it is suggested to take two characteristics of the eye. The first is fixing the eye on a specific point on the display. The second is the moment when the eyeball moves when moving the view from one point to another. The program evaluates the data obtained and determines unique characteristics for each case, i.e., for each person including the work of the eyeball muscles. The second characteristic is used only in industrial versions for special purposes and uses an expensive solution – the so-called Solvers, which help to determine the coincidence of characteristics in an acceptable time of 3-5 seconds. Using a smartphone with a camera attachment and the *Peek* software application, the procedure for removing the retinal picture is performed. Through the *Wiegand* data transfer interface and *API* functions of the application, information from the retinal image is transferred to a database or temporary file, where data is read and processed (Givoino & Rostovtsev, 2016).

To date, there are two newly developed algorithms to segment blood vessels:

- a method based on the use of a median filter,
- a method based on the use of a series of *Gabor* filters.

The results of testing these algorithms on two retinal databases demonstrate the possibility to use the first one for biometric authentication systems. The second method requires large computational costs, so it is not suitable for biometric authentication systems in the framework of the problem under consideration (Nafikov, 2016).

However, at the moment, the most stable algorithm with minimal errors of the first and second level (based on testing and practical experiments) is the algorithm based on the search for branching points. This algorithm searches for branching points in the blood vessel system. At the same time, it is more specialized in finding bifurcation and intersection points and much more resistant to noise, but it can only work on binary images. To search for points, segmented vessels are compressed to the thickness of one pixel. Thus, each point of the vessels can be classified by the number of neighbours. This algorithm requires much less computational resources compared to the algorithm based on the phase correlation method. In addition, there are opportunities for its complication to minimize the probability of hacking the system (Authentication via the retina of the eye).

Genetic factors do not actually determine the composition of the blood vessel's structure (the intersection of which creates the desired second matrix) on the human retina. In other words, the structure of the retina (the location of blood vessels) is not reflected in the human DNA and, accordingly, is not an inherited trait, which significantly affects the stability of the algorithm to erroneous access. Up to 400 unique features, from which a map of changes is created according to a given algorithm (or a second matrix for transforming the data of the first matrix into a third one), can be obtained from the retina. The size of the stored information about these unique features is only 96 bytes and is considered the smallest biometric template, which, in turn, allows to minimize the cost of resources (including computational and time), but is not suitable to create and implement the data transformation algorithm of the first matrix due to the critically small size and inconsistency with the selected algorithm for crossing blood vessels, but makes it possible to assess the degree of value of the processed information.

The small size of the primary change map to implement the original transformation of the first matrix into the third allows strengthening the algorithm without significant loss of resources. There are two ways to work with the change map: using the change map recursively or with an additional transformation algorithm. Both methods internally have the format of changing the original second matrix in one way or another and can be used simultaneously to strengthen the protection of an electronic document and reduce the probability of erroneous access

and authentication of a person.

When developing and implementing an enhanced algorithm to read the intersections of blood vessels in the retina, it is necessary to take into account both the speed of the system to process the algorithm as a whole and use autonomous data exclusively, i.e., to use keys or encryption methods on a third-party resource in this task is not possible and contradicts the very principle of creating an autonomous electronic document to identify a person.

The use of this algorithm for recording identification and information data about a person is optimal to use an additional function, namely, modifying an existing file (e.g., an existing graphic image) with the introduction of data from the third (already transformed) matrix using the second matrix as a map of changes. This leads to additional requirements for the storage files used, such as document size, readability and use on various platforms and operating systems without loss of quality, the ability to cloud storage and storage in the memory of any technical device.

This algorithm allows not only to create a secure electronic document for identifying and authenticating a person but also to modify the form of storing any document that requires data concealment. For example, if a file is needed to encrypt, it can be placed inside any user-friendly image as described above and stored in the public domain, provided that only the user knows, which graphic image contains the desired file, and can decrypt it unambiguously way according to their biometric parameters.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that the proposed concept, in contrast to existing solutions, allows creating a fundamentally new way to both use and store identity documents based on biometric parameters, which, in turn, significantly reduces the risks of erroneous verification, errors in access rights and identification, economic and other resource costs to use identification documents, it makes possible a full-fledged transition from plural of different types certifying and confirming social and legal rights of a citizen to a single electronic document.

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Spiritual-moral and artistic-aesthetic education of the creative personality in the process of training bachelors in the field of art embroidery

Abstract:

Due to the constant and rapid updating of technologies, the process of personal formation and cultural development of students, their outlook and value system, spiritual and creative potential increases in the conditions of social, economic, political, scientific and technical changes taking place in modern society. The modern stage of social development is characterized by an accelerated pace of development of technology and technology. The application of new techniques in the field of technical and technological creativity and the solution of problems in this area depends on basic knowledge, mental qualities of a person, knowledge of working methods and prerequisites for successful creative activity. Arts bachelor training is especially relevant and can give society new strength on the path of economic, social and spiritual development. The article attempts to formulate two actual problems in pedagogical science. The author believes that the formation of personality in the system of spiritual, moral, artistic and aesthetic education of students is currently one of the priorities of state policy in the field of education and culture, and the formation of technological training of bachelors is possible only when performing practical tasks of various levels of complexity and joint research activities with the teacher.

Keywords:

moral and aesthetic education, aesthetic culture, technological training, art embroidery.

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Духовно-нравственное и художественно-эстетическое воспитание творческой личности в процессе подготовки бакалавров в области художественной вышивки

Аннотация:

Благодаря постоянному и быстрому обновлению технологий, процесс личностного становления и культурного развития студентов, их мировоззрения и системы ценностей, духовного и творческого потенциала возрастает в условиях социально-экономических, политических, научно-технических изменений, происходящих в современном обществе. Современный этап общественного развития характеризуется ускоренными темпами развития техники и технологий. Применение новых методик в области технического и технологического творчества и решение проблем в этой области зависит от базовых знаний, умственных качеств человека, знания методов работы и предпосылок для успешной творческой деятельности. Подготовка бакалавров искусств особенно актуальна и может придать обществу новые силы на пути экономического, социального и духовного развития. В статье предпринята попытка сформулировать две актуальные проблемы педагогической науки. Автор считает, что формирование личности в системе духовно-нравственного, художественно-эстетического воспитания учащихся в настоящее время является одним из приоритетов государственной политики в области образования и культуры, а формирование технологической подготовки бакалавров возможно только при выполнении практических заданий различного уровня сложности и совместной научно-исследовательской деятельности с преподавателем.

Ключевые слова:

нравственно-эстетическое воспитание, эстетическая культура, технологическая подготовка, художественная вышивка.

Introduction

In the life of modern society, education plays a major role, as it is the main source of generating, improving and developing human capital.

Due to the constant and rapid updates of technologies, the process of personal formation and cultural development of students, their worldview and value system, spiritual and creative potential increases in the conditions of social and economic, political, scientific and technological changes taking place in modern society. The current stage of social development is characterized by an accelerated pace of development of equipment and technologies. New ideas are constantly needed to create competitive products and train highly qualified personnel. The application of new techniques in the field of technical and technological creativity and solving

problems in this area depends on the basic knowledge, mental qualities of a person, knowledge of working methods and prerequisites for successful creative activity. Students, as the most progressive part of the youth, due to their educational level and active working age, who have a non-standard 'view' of the surrounding reality, will take the place of the main intellectual and creative productive force of society in the nearest future. The training of bachelor artists is particularly relevant and can give society new strength on the path of economic, social and spiritual development.

1. Relevance of personality formation in the system of spiritual, moral, artistic and aesthetic education of students

It should be noted that the artistic and aesthetic culture of the individual is an effective way of moral transformation, both of the individual and of society as a whole. The inner beauty of the soul and a special sense of connection with the surrounding world, the creative orientation of young person's artistic activity is a necessary condition for the harmonious development of his personality.

The formation of personality in the system of spiritual, moral, artistic and aesthetic education of students is currently one of the priorities of state policy in the field of education and culture, which is reflected in the Federal Law of *Education in the Russian Federation*, the concept of the federal target program *Youth of Russia* for 2020, the federal program *Culture of Russia* for 2016-2020.

It should be noted that the need for ready-made works of modern traditional applied art with art embroidery that have artistic and aesthetic value, can be met only through high-quality and professional training of students, future professionals in this field.

The understanding of the essence of moral and aesthetic representations is based on two fundamental categories – 'morality' and 'aesthetics'. In philosophical encyclopedia, morality is defined as one of the most important and essential factors of social life. Morality consists in voluntary amateur coordination of feelings, aspirations and actions of society members with the feelings, aspirations and actions of fellow citizens, their interest and dignity, with the interest and dignity of the whole society (Kairov & Bogdanova, 1980).

From the point of view of *S.I. Ozhegov*, "morality is the internal spiritual qualities that guide a person, ethical norms, rules of behaviour determined by these qualities" (Ozhegov, 2006). Moral and aesthetic culture is the most important component of the spiritual development of the individual. Their presence in a person depends on his intelligence, creative orientation and the special attitude to the world. Moral and

aesthetic education is a part of the general system of personal education, which involves education in the process of artistic activity.

In the period of modernization of higher professional schools, there is a problem of preparing bachelors, future artists of traditional applied art for professional activities, developing their creative thinking, creating high-demand professional products with art embroidery. Successful work of a modern bachelor artist requires knowledge of various techniques and technologies to perform artistic embroidery taking into account local historical artistic traditions, awareness of the current state and development of modern high fashion. The formation of personal morality is carried out through the education of moral qualities, creative features and the disclosure of the student's personality. Organizing the process of moral-aesthetic priorities' formation in today's environment, you must always remember about the impact of factors at different levels on the personality of the future bachelor artist: scientific and technical, social, regional, environmental, conditions of the Higher School of Folk Arts (Academy), the Faculty of Applied Art, the Department of Art Embroidery, the characteristics of the teaching staff, their skills, personal qualities of the student internal state.

Thus, the moral transformation of a person and society, the relationship with the surrounding world, the creative orientation of artistic activity is a necessary condition for the harmonious development of the individual and readiness to create highly professional works of art with artistic embroidery is possible only through high-quality and professional training. Personal morality is carried out through the aesthetic education of moral qualities, creative features and the disclosure of the student's personality.

2. Disclosure of the essence of aesthetic education and culture

Thinkers of different centuries interpreted the concepts of morality, ethics, and the ideal in different ways. In the works of Aristotle on the moral man, it was said: "Morally beautiful is called a person of perfect dignity. After all, they speak about moral beauty about virtue: courageous, prudent person generally possessing all the virtues is called morally beautiful" (Kairov & Bogdanova, 1980). The concepts of 'morality', 'ethics', and 'aesthetics' are similar in meaning, but they originated in three different languages.

Aesthetic education is a very broad concept. It includes the education of an aesthetic attitude to nature, work, social life, everyday life, and art.

In the process of the realization of aesthetic education, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- systematically develop the aesthetic perception, feelings and representations of the students, their artistic and creative abilities;
- form the basis of aesthetic taste.

Aesthetic education is the most important aspect of education. It helps to enrich the sensory experience, the emotional sphere of the individual, affects the knowledge of the moral side of reality and increases cognitive activity. It is very important that the educational process is carried out on a scientific basis and according to a specific program taking into account the current level of development of traditional applied art in the field of art embroidery in compliance with the principle of gradualism, consistent complexity of requirements, and a differentiated approach to knowledge and skills.

Aesthetic education is closely connected with modernity, the desire to transform the world around us, society, nature, the subject environment, the ability to respond to beauty and create according to the laws of beauty in all spheres of human life. Aesthetic culture of the individual means the unity of aesthetic knowledge, beliefs, feelings, skills, norms of activity and behaviour. Aesthetic culture has the following functions:

- informational-cognitive, value-oriented, active-volitional one, which is implemented in aesthetic abilities;
- communicative-regulatory, which is manifested in emotional and normative self-regulation of behaviour and activity of the individual (Meshcheryakova & Zinchenko, 2003).

The main requirements for the process to form the moral and aesthetic culture of the individual are:

- aesthetic perception and feelings, aesthetic taste, aesthetic need, aesthetic activity, which becomes the basis for identifying pedagogical means of their development;
- age features, which consist of the flexibility of imagination, disposition to creativity.

The choice of content, methods and means of training bachelor artists is based on the integration processes of various types of artistic and creative activities: visual, applied, musical, speech, theatrical ones, which form the ability to feel and perceive aesthetic values.

Thus, the goal of moral education is a set of moral qualities of the individual that determine the behaviour and attitude of the individual to the surrounding reality,

other people and himself, and based on the system of moral values of the socio-cultural space, in which this person exists.

The term 'aesthetics' comes from the Greek 'aisteticos', i.e., feeling, sensual. Following definition is in the *S.I. Ozhegov's* explanatory dictionary, "Aesthetics is philosophical teaching about the essence and forms of beauty in artistic creation, nature and life, about art as a special kind of social ideology." (Ozhegov2006)

In the brief dictionary of aesthetics, we can read that "aesthetics is the science that studies the nature, the basic laws of development and functioning of the aesthetic in nature and society, material and spiritual production, lifestyle, people, aesthetic consciousness' forms, the basic laws of occurrence, development and place in society art as the highest forms of aesthetic. An integral part of aesthetics is the theory of aesthetic education." (Akonshina et al., 2003)

Scientists give many interpretations of the concept of 'aesthetic education'. In the research of *S.M. Vishnyakova*, "aesthetic education is a purposeful process to form a creatively active person able to perceive, feel, evaluate the beautiful, tragic, comic, ugly in life and art, live and create according to the laws of beauty." (Vishnyakova, 2000) In the Brief Dictionary of Aesthetics, its education is defined as "a system of activities aimed at developing and improving a person's ability to perceive, correctly understand, appreciate and create the beautiful and sublime in life and art" (Akonshina et al., 2003). *Y.S. Lyubimova* said that "aesthetic education is a purposeful system of effective formation of a man capable of the social and aesthetic ideal to perceive and appreciate the beautiful, perfect, harmonious in life and art, able to live and work according to the laws of beauty." (Lyubimova, 2008)

Consequently, the ability to live and create 'according to the laws of beauty' aims the entire system of aesthetic and educational work to form an aesthetically active and creative personality, but not a passive contemplative personality.

Various creative activities contribute to develop thinking, imagination, will, organization and perseverance. According to *M.M. Rukavitsyn*, the ultimate goal of aesthetic education is a harmonious personality and a fully developed person, i.e., educated, progressive, highly moral man with the ability to work, the desire to create and understand the beauty of art (Rukavitsyn, 2002).

Thus, considering the moral and aesthetic sphere of the individual, we can conclude that moral and aesthetic education is a single process, in which both spheres are connected by a common foundation, i.e., the goal to develop the spiritual sphere of the individual, his harmonization and socialization.

Moral and aesthetic education is a labour-intensive process of forming and developing values, views, and ideals of the individual; tastes of the younger

generation. According to *O.V. Larmin*, the purpose of moral and aesthetic education is to form the consciousness and activity of people in the spirit of high, continuously creatively developing moral and aesthetic ideas (Volkov, 2008), which are integral components of spiritual culture.

The formation of moral and aesthetic ideas, the development of the individual emotional sphere, the transfer of necessary artistic knowledge and the development of their creative potential is carried out through education. Moral and aesthetic education occupies an important place in the entire system of the educational process since it is the development of aesthetic and moral ideas of the individual as a whole.

It should be noted that aesthetic education contributes to the enrichment of sensory experience and emotional personality, increases cognitive activity observing the principles of consistent complexity of the requirements of a differentiated approach to knowledge and skills in the field of art embroidery. There is the formation of a creatively active person, who can perceive, feel, evaluate and ‘create according to the laws of beauty’. The creative process through education and training, as we see, contributes to the highly artistic training of future bachelor artists.

3. Features of formation of educational and cognitive activity in modern conditions

Creative learning in the modern traditional and applied art, for example, lessons on the technology of art embroidery and performing skills, also combining different techniques contribute to the highly artistic training of future bachelors and have great creative potential, as well as educational and developmental opportunities that should be implemented in the pedagogical process (Nosan, 2012). According to the concept of *P.R. Atutov*, academician of the Russian Academy of Education, the technology combines nature- and culture-forming functions and becomes associated with the entire system ‘nature-practice-man-science’, and “in a broad sense, technology is interpreted as a transformative human activity, but not only as an activity related to material production” (Atutov, 1997).

Researchers *Y.L. Khotuntsev* and *O.V. Kozhin* defined technology in the aspect of production activity “...as knowledge about the optimal transformation of materials in the interests of man”. The subject orientation of technology training is to develop skills of high-quality work when creating products that are in demand “...technology provides certain technical information and develops skills that help to understand the technological world” (Nosan, 2012).

In modern conditions, there is an active integration of modern trends in art and design, the emergence of new trends and trends in art. There are also changes in folk

art, in particular in art embroidery with its stable regional traditions. These changes can be at the level of the composition structure, material, colouristic and technological techniques. The concept of 'technology' is an ordered set of methods, techniques, forms of organization of activities, equipment and tools, the use of which provides the solution of practical tasks and is evaluated according to criteria that determine the quality of the results obtained. The disciplines of *Technology and Materials Science* and *Performance Skills* have a practice-oriented orientation, practical activity is considered here as a means of the general development of the student, the formation of special, technological, universal methods and techniques of their activities in the educational process. Students' productive activities based on the technology of art embroidery and performing skills create a unique basis for personal self-realization. They correspond to the age characteristics of the mental development of bachelor artists, when, thanks to their productive performing activities, students can realize their skills, earn recognition for their conscientiousness in their work, perseverance in achieving the goal, as the authors of an original creative idea embodied in material form. As a result, it is here that the foundations of hard work and self-expression are laid, valuable practical skills, experience in transformative activities and creativity are formed. Classes in the technology of art embroidery and performing skills have unique opportunities for the spiritual and moral development of the individual: the development of creative abilities to perceive artistic values. Practical activity is considered as a means of general development. The formation of social personally significant qualities of the student, the formation of special, technological and universal-technological techniques creates a unique basis for self-realization of the individual showing perseverance in achieving the goal, or as the authors of an original creative idea embodied in material form. The education of spirituality is also promoted by the active study of images of decorative and applied art, art embroidery and natural objects, which are an inexhaustible source of ideas for bachelor artists. Familiarization with natural crafts, the study of folk cultural traditions also has a huge moral meaning.

The basis of the emerging educational and cognitive activity of bachelors is made up of visually-figurative and visually-effective samples of products from the fund of the Department of Art Embroidery. According to the main forms of training in art embroidery technology, it is necessary to use verbal (explanatory and illustrative), visual, practical and heuristic methods. Verbal one is a method of systematic and consistent discussion of the task, a specific difficult situation, its essence and meaning. Instruction is a type of training that always accompanies the implementation of practical work, research, and independent work.

Visual methods are always used in the classes of art embroidery technology and performance skills. The teacher demonstrates clarity in the form of illustrations when studying the properties of materials, the sequence of execution of products of various types of samples of decorative and applied art with art embroidery.

There can be art albums, art and graphic schemes depicting traditional embroidery techniques, drawings, photographs of historical samples of products, samples of collars, napkins, coupons of women's clothing made in various techniques of art embroidery from the department's fund, instruction cards, i.e., a series of drawings, diagrams indicating the order of the sequence of operations (Nosan, 2012). Practical methods of art embroidery technology training include:

- consolidation of the obtained theoretical knowledge, skills, performing exercises – performing, repeated repetitions of practical actions according to a given pattern;
- partially search method that includes elements of reproductive and search activity (Babansky, 2002).

The correct use of methods allows to organize the process of learning the technology of art embroidery excitingly, form a student's attitude to himself (honesty), others (respect, responsiveness), work (responsibility), and nature (careful attitude). After analyzing the methodological foundations of moral and aesthetic education, we can identify methods that contribute to the effective development of moral and aesthetic ideas. To develop a cognitive indicator, we should use the following methods: story, explanation, instruction, illustrations (diagrams, instructional maps). The emotional and value indicator will be developed through the use of such methods as ethical conversation, illustrations, and demonstration of a sample model in the classroom. To optimize the bachelor's educational activities and successfully implement the tasks of moral and aesthetic education, it is necessary to take into account the specifics of conducting classes in technology. We should know what can contribute to the formation of moral and aesthetic ideas and the development of students' creativity. The curriculum of *Technology and Materials Science of Art Embroidery* and *Performance Skills* are the basic academic disciplines to train artists in this field. The method of teaching art embroidery technology is based on the joint integrated activity of the teacher and the student to identify the aesthetic and technological features of a particular exhibit-sample.

An important role is played by the level of training of the teacher, his creative personality type, pedagogical orientation, psychological and emotional competence, creating special audio and visual environment in the classroom; 'immersion' in the

problem being studied: viewing, listening, inventing. Before classes on art embroidery technology and performing skills, students get detailed information about traditional centres of art embroidery in Novgorod, Olonets, Ivanovo, Gorky (Nizhny Novgorod), Moscow, Ryazan, get acquainted with their characteristic features, which are expressed in the technology of performance, compositional structure, colouristic and stylistic features. Students also learn to compare and analyze historical patterns and other types of embroidery.

Illustrative material (photos from museums, albums, and online resources) and educational samples from the methodological fund are provided for this work. The study of the content of the discipline of *Technology and Materials Science of Art Embroidery* is carried out by students in the first year of study. This is the necessary theoretical information related to the topics of all specialized disciplines.

Thus, the above list of works indicates a complex and time-consuming process that requires students to focus, attention, and skill in performing, which contributes to improving their professional level. As an example, Table 1 shows the topics of classes on art embroidery technology and performance skills (see Appendix).

4. Structure and types of classes teaching art embroidery technology

There should be a special organizational introductory part aimed at providing an understanding of the essence and procedure to perform practical work on the independent activity of converting material into a product.

The theoretical part should be organized dynamically and entertainingly. It is necessary to rely on the professional experience of the teacher and students (integrated activities of the teacher and the student to identify the historical, aesthetic and technological features of a particular exhibit-task), the need for a quality level of the teacher. At each stage of the lesson, we should consolidate the skills of work culture:

- properly organize the workplace;
- make a sequence-a work plan – select materials, choose tools, observe order in the workplace;
- perform the task efficiently, accurately and accurately bring what you started to completion;
- economically spend materials, use tools and devices efficiently, time;
- strictly follow the safety rules when working with tools and devices;
- monitor the correctness of the task;
- find errors and correct them if possible.

When choosing a product to perform, it should be taken into account that they must be diverse in their execution technology, have different opportunities for moral and aesthetic impact on the student. To teach the technology of art embroidery, the following types of classes should be used:

- a theoretical lesson,
- a lesson to consolidate the studied theoretical knowledge or the development of practical skills;
- a practical, combined, control lesson, an excursion lesson.

Structure of the combined technology lesson is the main one and consists of the following stages:

- motivational (communicating the goals and objectives of the lesson), reviewing and analyzing a sample, sketch, drawing, encouraging activity, creating an exclusive product, discussing issues of moral and aesthetic orientation;
- organizational (planning, instruction and the study of schemes, study of safety regulations, organization of the workplace);
- practical (independent work, control and correction of labour movements and actions);
- control and evaluation (summing up and evaluating the final results of activities) (Atutov, 1997).

In the organization of art embroidery technology classes, which form the moral and aesthetic ideas of the student, the most important stage is motivational. When the analysis of the sample, the ability to aesthetic and subject creative activity develops, in addition to fact that an aesthetic and moral assessment, aesthetic judgment (when discussing the appearance of the sample: ‘beautiful’ – ‘not beautiful’, what feelings and emotions are caused by the object), attitude to the surrounding world also form. In the course of an ethical conversation, the teacher’s story, at this stage, students learn to clearly express their judgment about the subject, compare their assessment with the assessment of others, enrich their ideas about the beauty of products with artistic embroidery, their significance in the lives of others.

Thus, the purpose of professional education is to develop students’ readiness for artistic and technological activities in the field of traditional applied arts, creation of material and spiritual values, development of personal abilities, striving for improvement. Table 2 (see Appendix) provides recommendations on how to develop functional maps, tables for studying operations and their constituent techniques:

1. Analysis of the content of the program topic and selection of subtopics – types of operations that are disclosed in a separate map;
2. Defining the components of the exercise map.

Conclusion

*Thus, as we can conclude from the above, moral and aesthetic representation develops more successfully when creating a special atmosphere in the classroom in the process of performing a task that relieves tension as a result of emotional experience and exposure to the senses. The discipline of *Technology and Materials Science* provides real inclusion various structural components of the individual in the educational process: intellectual, emotional and aesthetic, spiritual and moral and physical. In their unity creating conditions for harmonizing the development, preservation and promotion of mental health of the younger generation, the course of technology art of embroidery skill and performance is effective from the point of view of the development of the moral aesthetic and technological bases of creativity of bachelors' professional training. The results of students' practical activities are evaluated according to Table 3 (see Appendix).*

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Appendix

Table 1. Development of artistic and technological techniques of artistic embroidery in the regions

№	Region	Type of art embroidery	Features of art embroidery	Specifics of professional train
1. 1.1 .	Vladimir region: Mstera	White surface	Color: white fabric, white threads. White smooth surface is performed in combination with other types of embroidery: a stalk seam, a smooth surface with a split, knots with a winding, a pyshechka, a polka dot, a placer, a lining (blown) seam, openwork cuts, banners, stitch seams that give plant patterns openwork and lightness. Compositional features – miniature plant patterns, with exquisite garlands and bouquets of wild herbs and flowers. The most common image here is of a rose surrounded by small flowers and leaves gathered in garlands or small bouquets. Genre scenes depicting castles, elegant ladies and	Materials: awning, cambric, chiffon, silk. Sequence of execution: the contour of the drawing is sewn with frequent stitches ‘forward needle’ or stalk seam, perform large stitches flooring (inside each form), then cover it with tightly laid parallel stitches of double-sided smoothness to obtain a convex texture. Smooth surface with a split, knots with a winding, placer, pyshechka, polka dots lining, slotted smooth surface (embroider a very thin needle). The contour is sewn forward with a needle or a stalk seam.

			gentlemen, fairy-tale birds, swans.	
2.	Novgorod region: Kresttsy	Krestetskaya stitch	Color: white fabric, white threads. Krestetsky seams: loose guipure, old guipure, soap bubble, Vologda glass, tarlata, simple and complex earrings: bug, simple town, punk, counting surface, medallions, cobweb, kopecks, fan, crackers. Elegant geometric shapes consisting of a complex interweaving of rhombuses, rosettes, and stars, inscribed in the background of the lightest grids.	Materials: marquisette, cambric, wool, silk, (embroidered with a thin needle). The sequence of execution: marking, pre-roller, pruning, holding, netting, flooring on the grid, single, double darning, air loop, spider, spider web, cracker, penny, leaves, squares with overlap, hoof, medallions, cut-out, edge teeth, roller.

Table 2. Recommendations on developing functional maps, tables for studying operations and their constituent techniques

Functional map to perform art embroidery exercises	
<p>Exercise 1. The study of the art of embroidery Colored Perevit'</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Color Perevit' – general information about the variety of this type of stitch embroidery, its features. Centers for the distribution of colored perevit'. Originality technological methods: 'stan', 'deck', previt', paint, smooth surface, 'set', drawn thread work. Regional features of coloristic performance of colored perevit'. Variety of subjects, motifs, ornaments. 2. Practical task: performing routing for the execution of the process sequence of embroidery the corner of the swipe in the technique of colored perevit': <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. draw a sheet of Whatman according to the size of the corner element format into cells with a size of 0.2 X 0.2 cm. for the calculation scheme; b. perform the layout of the counting schemes of cutting in the prepared format for the corner element; c. perform a technical audit scheme for napkins in the technique of 'paint', smooth surface, 'set', 'stan', "deck", perevit', drawn thread work; d. perform and draw step-by-step technological scheme for receiving embroidery on a landscape sheet of A-4 format: a sequence of 'paint', smooth surface, 'set', 'stlan', 'deck', perevit', drawn thread work, cage dimension: 0.2 on 0.2 or 0.3 on 0.3 cm. 3. Making a sample, a fragment of embroidery. 4. Drawing up an album with diagrams and samples of art embroidery. 	<p>Tools and materials:</p> <p>pencil, ruler, cutter, millimeter paper, tracing paper, albums, needles, floss threads of different shades, eraser, round embroidery frame, samples for laboratory and practical tasks using old regional embroidery.</p>

<p>Exercise 2. The study of the art of Ivanovo stitch embroidery</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ivanovo stitch – general information about the variety of this type of stitch embroidery, its features. Distribution centers of the Ivanovo stitch. Originality of technological techniques: ‘flooring’, ‘cracker’, ‘fan’, ‘spider’. Regional features of the coloristic execution of the ‘Ivanovo stitch’. Variety of subjects, motifs, and ornaments. 2. Practical task: implementation of the technological map for the execution of the technological sequence of embroidery of the corner element of the napkin in the technique of Ivanovo stitch. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. draw a sheet of Whatman according to the size of the corner element format into cells with a size of 0.2 X 0.2 cm. for the calculation scheme; b. mark up the counting schemes of the cuttings in the prepared format for the corner element; c. perform the technical counting scheme for the napkin in the technique: ‘flooring’, ‘cracker’, ‘fan’, ‘spider’, drawn thread work; d. perform and draw step-by-step technological scheme for receiving embroidery on a landscape sheet of A-4 format: ‘flooring’, ‘cracker’, ‘fan’, ‘spider’, drawn thread work; cage size: 0.2 on 0.2 or 0.3 on 0.3 cm. 3. Making a sample of an embroidery fragment: ‘deck’, ‘cracker’, ‘fan’, ‘spider’, drawn thread work. 4. Drawing up an album with diagrams and samples of art embroidery: ‘flooring’, ‘cracker’, ‘fan’, ‘spider’, drawn thread work. 	<p>Tools and materials:</p> <p>Pencil, ruler, cutter, millimeter paper, tracing paper, albums, needles, floss threads of different shades, eraser, round embroidery frames, samples for laboratory and practical tasks using old regional embroidery.</p>
<p>Exercise 3. The study of the art of Kadom veniz embroidery</p> <p>Kadom veniz – general information about the variety of this type of stitch embroidery, its features. Centers of distribution of Kadom veniz embroidery. Originality of technological techniques: a unique needle embroidery in white on white – veniz, (resembling expensive needle lace), and is performed as a contour seam forward needle or stalk, smooth surface with flooring, double-sided smooth surface with locks, cutout of fabric for cutting, throwing warps, spiders, navels, kopecks, leaves, stars, cucumbers, with elements of needle lace, ‘knots with winding’, ‘placer’, ‘blown’, slotted surface, festoons, holes (embroider a very thin needle), seam covering twist. At the same time, the cuts that were previously studied in stitch sewing are used: white stitch, white smooth surface, stitch openwork, openwork cuts, banners, openwork backgrounds, white stitch on a small grid with complex earrings, semi-cross – painting, white stitch on a small grid with complex drawn thread work.</p> <p>Regional features of coloristic performance of Kadom veniz. Variety of subjects, motifs, ornaments.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Practical task: performing routing for the execution of the embroidery process sequence of corner swipe technique: ‘Kadom veniz’: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. draw a sheet of Whatman according to the size of the corner element format into cells with a size of 0.2 on 0.2 cm for the calculation scheme; 	<p>Tools and materials:</p> <p>Pencil, ruler, cutter, millimeter paper, tracing paper, albums, needles, floss threads of different shades, eraser, round embroidery frames, samples for laboratory and practical tasks using old regional embroidery.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b. perform the layout of the counting schemes of cutting in the prepared format for the corner element; c. perform a technical audit scheme for napkins in the technique of 'Kadom venise' drawn thread work; d. perform and draw step-by-step technological scheme for receiving embroidery on a landscape sheet of A-4 format: a sequence of 'paint', smooth surface, 'set', 'stlan', 'deck', perevit', drawn thread work, cage dimension: 0.2 on 0.2 or 0.3 on 0.3 cm. <p>2. Execution of a sample, a fragment of Kadomsky veniz embroidery.</p> <p>3. Drawing up an album with diagrams and samples of art embroidery in the 'Kadom veniz' technique.</p>	
<p>The approximate items of work: Study of regional embroidery techniques corresponding to the course program of <i>Art Embroidery Technology</i>. Making sketches and samples of embroidery in the material, a fragment of embroidery, drawing up an album with diagrams and samples of art embroidery.</p>	

Table 3. Example of a level description of indicators of professional training of art embroidery artists-bachelors

Indicators	I Infantile level	II Reproductive level	III Productive level	IV Creative level
Compliance of the execution technology with stitch embroidery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - grid cells of different sizes, columns are loosely wrapped, the smooth roller is not uniform over the entire length, has nodules; - cutting distort the cells of the grid; - 'kopeck' has an elongated shape, the last turn is not fixed in the 'kopeck' element, all kopecks are of different sizes; - single and double darning do not divide the cage into equal 2-3 parts, non-woven thread passing under each 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - some grid cells are of different sizes, the columns are loosely wrapped, the smooth roller is uneven along the entire length, has nodules; - cutting distort the cells of the grid; - 'kopeck' has an elongated shape, the last turn is not fixed in the 'kopeck' element, all kopecks are of different sizes; - single and double darning should not divide the cage into equal 2-3 parts, non-woven thread passing under each column, loosely 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - some cells of the grid are the same size, the columns are not completely wrapped tightly; the smooth roller is uniform along the entire length; - cuts slightly distort the grid cells; - 'kopeck' has a somewhat elongated shape, the last turn is weakly fixed in the 'kopeck' element; - single and double darning divides the cage into equal 2-3 parts, not quite smooth and not everywhere intertwined with a thread passing under 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - grid cells of the same size; - the posts are tightly wrapped; - smooth roller uniform along the entire length; - smooth roller without cuts and skips of threads; - cuts do not distort the grid cells; - the 'kopeck' is made in an even circle; the last turn must be fixed in the 'kopeck' element; - single and double darning divides the cage into equal 2-3 parts, smooth and intertwined with a thread passing under each column;

	<p>column, loosely wrapped; - floorings are tightened in a grid cage, a cage of different size and density, which should be checked by piercing the completed fragment with a working needle; - the mats are poorly wrapped, the turns of threads do not fit together, and do not create the appearance of a single thread; - the elements on the four tiles are not symmetrical and distort the shape of a square or rectangle.</p>	<p>wrapped; - floorings are tightened in a mesh cage, a cage of different size and density, which should be checked by piercing the completed fragment with a working needle; - the mats are carelessly wrapped, the turns of the threads do not fit well together, and they do not create the appearance of a single thread; - the elements on the four tiles are not symmetrical and distort the shape of a square or rectangle.</p>	<p>each column; - floorings are unevenly stretched in the grid cell, the cell is of different size and density, which should be checked by piercing the completed fragment with a working needle; - the mats are carelessly wrapped, the turns of threads fit loosely to each other, and do not create the appearance of a single thread; - the elements on the four tiles retain their symmetry, but in some places, they distort the shape of a square or rectangle; - embroidered elements do not pull the fabric together.</p>	<p>- floorings are evenly stretched in a grid cage of the same size and density, which should be checked by piercing the completed fragment with a working needle; - the mats are neatly wrapped with tightly fitting turns of threads to each other, and create the appearance of a single thread; - the elements on the four tiles retain their symmetry and do not distort the shape of a square or rectangle; - the symmetry of the drawing is not broken; all elements of the drawing are finished; - there are no loops or knots on the front side of the embroidery; - no skewing of the material when pouring; - the ends of the 'Brid' are well fixed.</p>
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Ethno-pedagogical theories of the 19th century and Slavophile philosophy (in Russian)

Abstract:

The current social processes taking place in the world are diverse and contradictory. Globalization on the one hand and ultra-national movements on the other. How much the presence or absence of a national, Russian origin in children's pedagogy, in his environment, brought up in him a love for the Motherland, for Russia. How unique and necessary is folk pedagogy in the formation of a Russian person. The author of the article examines the main ethno-pedagogical theories of the 19th century and their relationship with the philosophy of the Slavophiles. The author concludes that the philosophy of the Slavophiles is permeated with love for Russia and its rich historical and cultural heritage. In the current time, it is necessary to develop the ideas of ethno-pedagogy and include Russian culture and folk traditions in the modern educational system.

Keywords:

ethno-pedagogical theories, philosophy of the Slavophiles, ethno-pedagogy, ethnic education.

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Этнопедагогические теории XIX века и философия славянофилов

Аннотация:

Текущие социальные процессы, протекающие в мире, являются разнообразными и противоречивыми. Глобализация с одной стороны и ультранациональные движения с

другой. Насколько наличие или отсутствие национального, русского начала в детской педагогике, в его окружении воспитало в нём любовь к Родине, к России. Насколько уникальна и необходима народная педагогика в становлении русского человека. Автор статьи рассматривает основные этнопедагогические теории XIX века и их взаимосвязь с философией славянофилов. Автор делает заключение, что философия славянофилов пронизана любовью к России и к её богатейшему историческому и культурному наследию. В текущем времени необходимо развивать идеи этнопедагогике и включать русскую культуру, народные традиции в современную образовательную систему.

Ключевые слова:

этнопедагогические теории, философия славянофилов, этнопедагогика.

Введение

Текущие социальные процессы, протекающие в мире, являются разнообразными и противоречивыми. Глобализация с одной стороны и ультранациональные движения с другой. Именно сейчас ученые, философы и педагоги подчеркивают актуальность влияния воспитания и образование детей и подростков на формировании личности человека в целом и гражданина России в частности.

Насколько наличие или отсутствие национального, русского начала в детской педагогике, в его окружении воспитало в нём любовь к Родине, к России. Насколько уникальна и необходима народная педагогика в становлении русского человека. И разительно ли отличается педагогика русского народа от педагогики других народов. Все эти вопросы не утратили своей актуальности с XIX века. Уже тогда не утихали споры про истоки народной культуры и пути развития России через призму образования.

Данная работа рассматривает основные этнопедагогические теории XIX века и их взаимосвязь с философией славянофилов. Народная педагогика, как фактор воспитания личности в культурной связи со своей страной, находит отражение во взглядах Владимира Фёдоровича Одоевского, Ивана Васильевича Киреевского, Константина Сергеевича Аксакова, Алексея Степановича Хомякова и других. Пётр Григорьевич Редкин и его ученик Константин Дмитриевич Ушинский писали о необходимости философской базы для педагогики и обосновали базовый принцип этнопедагогике – восприятие культуры своего народа через родной язык.

О народной педагогике стали писать ещё в XVII веке, а становление ее как объекта изучения наукой происходит во второй половине XX века, в том

числе в работах Г.Н. Волкова «Этнопедагогика» и «Чувашская народная педагогика», в работах Л.Н. Бережневой, Г.В. Нездемковской, Э.Р. Хакимова, Н.Д. Булатовой.

Обсуждение взглядов славянофилов началось с журнального спора в 1891-1893 годах (В.С. Соловьёв, А.Н. Пыпин, Н.Н. Страхов и др.). В начале XX века Н.А. Бердяев, С.А. Вергеров, С.Н. Булгаков и другие рассматривали в основном идеи отдельных авторов-славянофилов А.С. Хомякова, К.С. Аксакова, И.В. Киреевского. Взгляды славянофилов на педагогику нашли отражение в кандидатских диссертационных работах И.В. Карлова, Н.А. Волковича, статьях Парилова О.В., Гребышева И.В. и многих других.

Целью работы является рассмотреть влияние этнопедагогических теорий на взгляды славянофилов в XIX веке.

1. Этнопедагогические теории XIX века

Подходя к исследованию этнопедагогических теорий XIX века, в первую очередь, необходимо прояснить понятия «этнопедагогика» и «народная педагогика». Эти понятия различны, хотя многие исследователи и часто используют их как синонимы. Понятие «этнопедагогика» ввел в научный оборот Г.Н. Волков. Народная педагогика не является наукой, а представляет собой свод правил и обычаев воспитания, которые сложились в той или иной нации и проверенных временем, тогда как этнопедагогика это – наука, изучающая особенности национального характера, сложившиеся под влиянием исторических условий, сохранившиеся благодаря национальной системе воспитания, и претерпевающую эволюцию вместе с условиями жизни и развитием педагогической культуры народа. «Этнопедагогика изучает процесс социального взаимодействия и общественно-народного воздействия, в ходе которого воспитывается, развивается личность, усваивающая социальные нормы, ценности, опыт, собирает и систематизирует народные знания о воспитании и обучении детей, народную мудрость, отраженную в религиозных учениях, сказках, сказаниях, былинах, притчах, песнях, загадках, пословицах, играх, игрушках и прочем, в семейном и общинном укладе жизни, быте, традициях, а также философско-этические, собственно педагогические мысли и воззрения, то есть весь педагогический потенциал, совокупный опыт историко-культурного формирования личности» (Волков, 1999).

По мнению Л.Н. Бережневой этнопедагогика – наука, изучающая эмпирический опыт этнических групп в области воспитания и образования детей, морально-этнических воззрений на исконные ценности семьи, рода,

племени, народности, нации. Включает в себя специфическое видение мира, особое состояние сознания (этнопедагогическое представление), особым образом организованную деятельность, стереотипы поведения, особую традиционную систему воспитания. А предметом этнопедагогики считают воспитательный процесс (Бережнова и др., 2013). С ними соглашается и Э.Р. Хакимов, он считает, что объектом этой отрасли науки является образовательный процесс. Предметом в этом случае при исследовании являются как четко целенаправленные, так и стихийные процессы освоения этнопедагогических знаний (Хакимов, 2007).

Народная педагогика большое внимание уделяла моральным нормам и этическим принципам в повседневной жизни. Ребёнок воспитывался в среде, где было уважительное отношение к старшим, где ценились справедливость и верность, почитался труд, и было презрительное отношение к бездельникам, воспитывалось бесстрашие перед врагами и обязательная помощь друзьям. Произведения устного народного творчества донесли до нас те требования, которые были заложены в них, способы и приемы обучения и воспитания (Меньшикова, 2018).

«Поучение князя Владимира Мономаха детям» – первый уникальный письменный памятник народной педагогики XII века. В нём перечисляются основные благодетели русского народа, которые должны воспитываться в детях. Как отмечает Г.В. Нездемковская «Следование традиционному воспитательному народному опыту на Руси в повседневной педагогической практике и работе школ наблюдается до XVII в.» (Нездемковская, 2009).

В народной педагогике воспитание ребенка не выделяли в отдельный процесс, а включали ребёнка в ежедневную обывательскую жизнь, где исподволь и передавали знания об окружающем мире и обществе, о взаимодействии живой и неживой природы, о добре и зле, о добродетелях и несправедливости. Неслучайно многие великие педагоги не раз обращались к народной педагогике, как к сокровищнице средств и методов воспитания. Так, швейцарский педагог XIX века И.Г. Песталоцци при обосновании принципа природосообразности учитывал народный опыт, положительное влияние труда на развитие на детей, который закладывает основы для нравственного, эстетического и умственного воспитания ребенка. Некоторые дидактические правила даны им в форме народных афоризмов, а в ряде случаев народные афоризмы составляют элемент дидактических положений (Меньшикова, 2018).

Константин Дмитриевич Ушинский в своей статье «О народности в общественном воспитании» писал: «В основании особенной идеи воспитания у каждого народа лежит, конечно, особенная идея о человеке, о том, каков должен быть человек по понятиям народа в известный период народного развития. Каждый народ имеет свой особенный идеал человека и требует от своего воспитания воспроизведения этого идеала в отдельных личностях. Идеал этот у каждого народа соответствует его характеру, определяется его общественной жизнью, развивается вместе с его развитием, и выяснение его составляет главнейшую задачу каждой народной литературы» и далее «есть одна только общая для всех прирожденная склонность, на которую всегда может рассчитывать воспитание: это то, что мы называем народностью. Как нет человека без самолюбия, так нет человека без любви к отечеству, и эта любовь дает воспитанию верный ключ к сердцу человека и могущественную опору для борьбы с его дурными природными, личными, семейными и родовыми склонностями. Обращаясь к народности, воспитание всегда найдет ответ и содействие в живом и сильном чувстве человека, которое действует гораздо сильнее убеждения, принятого одним умом, или привычки, вкорененной страхом наказаний. Вот основание того убеждения, которое мы высказали выше, что воспитание, если оно не хочет быть бессильным, должно быть народным» (Ушинский, 2015).

Чуть позже выхода в свет статьи К.Д. Ушинского и во времена отмены крепостного права в России, Л.Н. Толстой создаёт в Ясной Поляне школу для крестьянских детей, пишет «Азбуку» и «Новую Азбуку», и изучает влияние русских обычаев на воспитательный процесс в школе. Он отмечает необходимость включения в образовательный процесс в России национальных традиций русского народа, с его историческим прошлым, с его фольклором и народным искусством. Западные европейские страны прошли свой путь, отличный от России, поэтому система ценностей у русского народа отличается от системы ценностей западных стран. И именно эта уникальная система ценностей лежит в основе народной педагогики. Л.Н. Толстой выступал за создание народного образования и подчеркивал: «Потребность образования лежит в каждом человеке; народ любит и ищет образования, как любит и ищет воздуха для дыхания» (Толстой, 1974).

В течение XIX века зарубежными и российскими учеными было предпринято множество попыток научного изучения влияния традиционной педагогики на воспитание детей и молодежи.

2. Славянофильство как философское направление XIX века

Также, как и в рассуждениях касательно этнопедагогики, рассуждения о философии славянофилов необходимо начинать с рассмотрения понятийного аппарата. Само понятие «славянофиль» претерпевало изменения. Начиная как ироничное клише «западников» про своих оппонентов, только через несколько десятков лет оно потеряло это значение и стало восприниматься как полноценное название одному из течений общественной мысли России в XIX веке. Славянофильство – достаточно исследованное направление философской мысли. Учеными рассмотрены работы славянофилов как литературное наследие, культурно-историческое наследие, религиозное и социальное наследие.

Главными взглядами, объединяющие «славянофилов», были их идеи об уникальном историческом и культурологическом пути России. Они считали, что развитие страны шло до петровских реформ по собственному пути и этот путь должен отличаться и в дальнейшем от пути социально-политического развития Запада. В основу основ они поместили православие, самодержавие и патриархальность, при этом славянофильство было оппозиционным течением того времени.

Как пишет С.В. Лебедев в своем предисловии к книге И.С. Аксакова «Наше знамя – русская народность» «Патриотизм как основа славянофильства придал этому философскому и литературному направлению особенную силу, совершенно несопоставимую с реальной численностью самих теоретиков. ... Но при всем том, что сами родоначальники славянофильства действительно были небольшим кружком, говорить, что они подобно декабристам «страшно далеки от народа», не приходится» (Аксаков, 2008).

Славянофилы рассматривали различные аспекты социального и культурного развития страны, в том числе они рассматривали и образование, и его непосредственное воздействие на развитие и осмысление культуры. При этом разница в образовании в России и на Западе определяло своеобразие культуры России и западных стран. Только те идеи западной цивилизации могут быть заимствованы, которые отвечают национальным традициям и русским православным началам. Тогда и только тогда они могут быть уместны в России. «Всё существенное и истинное Запада усвоится нами, когда оно вырастет из нашего корня, будет следствием нашего развития, а не когда упадет к нам в виде противоречия всему строю нашего бытия». При соблюдении указанного условия заемное послужит во благо, а умственное рабство будет невозможно: «При обилии понятий, почерпнутых из народной жизни, при

богатстве внутреннего содержания никогда пользование чужими трудами не поработит мысли», – пишет Ю.Ф. Самарин (Парилов, 2015).

Поэтому, так часто в работах славянофилов процесс воспитания рассматривается почти синонимично процессу образования, и нацелен он на развитие целостной личности, которой близки духовные ценности русского народа – нравственность, трудолюбие, духовность.

Лидер славянофилов А.С. Хомяков при рассмотрении причин различия между Россией и Западом, опирался на социальную и культурную жизнь Древней Руси. Именно там он и искал источник уникального развития России. Алексей Степанович считал, что петровские реформы способствовали еще большему разрыву правящего класса и русского народа и утрату у первых чувства родной культуры. Поэтому он ратовал за образование, которое бы базировалось на родной культуре, было бы связано с жизнью народа, но было бы отдельно от государственной политики.

Иван Васильевич Киреевский противопоставлял просвещение Европы просвещению в России. В Европе просвещение формировалось в трех основных направлениях через форму христианства, влиянием античного образования и особым типом государственности. Россия же, считал славянофил, восприняв культуру от Византии, унаследовала более цельную традицию образования, ориентированную на глубину и цельность самосознания (Гребешев, 2015).

Константин Сергеевич Аксаков в своей статье «Два слова о народном обучении» отмечает, что широкие энциклопедические знания не гарантируют полноты знаний, они лишь дают «просвещенное доверие», которое нужно для коллективного труда, коллективного знания. Он так же отмечал необходимость народного образования, в основании которого лежала бы православная духовная традиция.

Славянофилы не только обсуждали влияние национальной культуры на развитие страны, они внесли огромный вклад в собирание и популяризацию народной художественной культуры. Петр Киреевский, младший брат Ивана Васильевича Киреевского, практически всю жизнь собирал русские песни, которые после его смерти были изданы в 11 томах. Владимир Иванович Даль, хоть и не был представителем славянофилов, разделял их взгляды о необходимости изучения собственного культурного наследия. Из-под его пера выходит уникальный труд «Толковый словарь живого великорусского языка», который, хоть и написан был без использования классических лингвистических форм, является подтверждением уникальности,

синонимического богатства, живости русского языка. Также В.И. Даль выпустил сборник русских пословиц.

Подъем интереса к русской народной культуре того времени был напрямую связан с работами славянофилов. В литературной жизни появляется внутренний запрос на народное. Многие литераторы, философы предпринимают этнографические экспедиции для собирания фольклора. Иван Михайлович Снегирев пишет труд «Русские простонародные праздники и суеверные обряды». Павел Николаевич Рыбников после своей экспедиции по Олонецкой губернии фиксирует былины, которые до сих пор рассказывают в крестьянской среде. Эта находка перевернула взгляд ученых на устное народное творчество русского народа. Его находку подтвердил и развил Александр Федорович Гильфердинг, который так же предпринял ряд поездок по Русскому Северу и зафиксировал несколько десятков новых былин в местах их бытования. Также по собиранию устного народного творчества работали П.В. Штейн, П.А. Бессонов, М.А. Стахович.

Софья Александровна Давыдова во второй половине XIX века предпринимает ряд поездок по внутренним губерниям Российской империи и пишет труд, который на многие годы стал уникальным, «Русское кружево и русские кружевницы. Исследование историческое, техническое и статистическое». Наталья Леонидовна Шабельская коллекционирует народные костюмы разных губерний и выпускает в конце XIX века «Собрание предметов русской старины».

Говоря о философских взглядах XIX века, невозможно не упомянуть выдающегося ученого, интеллектуала Владимира Васильевича Стасова. Он хорошо известен как музыкальный и художественных критик, однако у него много работ, которые требуют этнографического осмысления. Данная направленность его деятельности была мало изучена в советской и постсоветской науке. Однако, в 2019 году Александр Владимирович Пыжиков издает забытый труд В.В. Стасова «Происхождение русских былин» 1868 года и дает обширную вступительную статью «Неожиданный Владимир Стасов». В статье ярко представлены взгляды В.В. Стасова о русской, коренной культуре народа. Многие его идеи не подпадают не только под идеи западничества, но и славянофильства. Для первых истоки цивилизации лежали в Европе, для вторых в Киеве, как наследнике Византии. Владимир Стасов указывает же на восточные элементы, которые пронизывают и русские былины, песни, и архитектуру. Он указывает на индийско-магометанские формы архитектуры, которые находит в России, «столько сродные древнерусскому нашему стилю;

они всегда останавливали на себе мое внимание стройностью и прекрасной профилировкой куполов» (Пыжиков и Стасов, 2019).

Что касается былин, то в 1859 году вышло «Сказание о славном богатыре Еруслане Лазаревиче», которую В.В. Стасов сравнил с персидской поэмой «Шахнамэ» (Книга царей). В этих произведениях прослеживается практически единая сюжетная линия, различны лишь имена и географические названия, при этом жизнеописания царевича Рустема из поэмы намного более детально описаны, нежели жизнь Еруслана. В «Происхождении русских былин» автор находит восточное происхождение или по крайней мере влияние в таких былинах, как Добрыня, Садко, Иван Гостиный сын, Ставр-боярин, Соловей Будимирович, Илья Муромец и другие.

Восточное влияние на русскую культуру воспринималось многими как в России, так и на Западе, скорее, как негативный фактор, который говорил о «варварском» происхождении русской цивилизации, о её неполноценности. А.В. Пыжиков отмечает: «присутствие восточных влияний в древнерусской среде не являлось большим секретом на Западе. Ведущие исследователи указывали на это, только преимущественно в негативном ключе. Например, так оценивал схожесть знаменитый культуролог Карл Шнаазе (1798-1875 гг.) в своей восьмитомной «Истории изобразительных искусств» (т. 3). Другой ученый Франц Куглер (1808-1858 гг.) сведения о древнерусской культуре вообще поместил в разделе «Мугаммеданское искусство», тем самым, подчеркивая их родство; лишь сближение с Европой, по его убеждению, оказалось благотворным, «подтянуло настоящие художественные силы страны» (Пыжиков Александр Владимирович).

Однако, французский архитектор Виолле-ле-Дюк не соглашался с этой точкой зрения и был солидарен с В.В. Стасовым. В своей книге «Русское искусство. Его источники, составные элементы, его высшее развитие, его будущность» он указывает на самобытное искусство России, которое было обязано «своим происхождением слиянию арийского племени с семитическим». Автор «получил возможность отличить разные течения, слившиеся в одно на русской почве и создавшее, начиная с XII века, самобытное искусство, способное к развитию и близко относящееся к византийскому, с которым оно, однако не смешивалось» (Виолле-Ле-Дюк, 1879). В своём труде он рассматривает архитектуру, роспись России, находит общее и различное с искусством Запада и Византии. В заключении он пишет: «Мы знаем, что даже люди не малого ума восстают теперь против попыток возрождения и увековечения национальных искусств. Они думают, что

искусство всемирно, единично, и что тщетны старания придать самостоятельность его различным выражениям. На их глаза есть только искусство и, следовательно, одно только высшее выражение его, к которому всякий должен стремиться. В теории подобный взгляд очень соблазнителен; но на деле он роковым образом ведет к однообразию и подделкам... в искусствах самобытность есть самое драгоценное из качеств, потому что оно естественно. – Это существенное качество искажается иногда некоторыми влияниями; но, чтобы ни делали, народ хранит его, вопреки системам, модам и чуждому обучению» (Виолле-Ле-Дюк, 1879).

Развивая и дополняя философские теории славянофилов, Николай Яковлевич Данилевский представил стройную теорию русской культуры и искусства. В своей работе «Россия и Европа» он осуждает западников за их достаточно примитивный подход к формированию русской культуры, видя это в западном образовании правящих слоев России. Н.Я. Данилевский считал, что у западников «под национальным разумелось не национальное вообще, а специально русское национальное, которое было так бедно, ничтожно, особливо если смотреть на него с чужой точки зрения; а как же было не стать на эту чужую точку зрения людям, черпавшим поневоле все образование из чужого источника?» И в этих идеях, в противопоставлении «узконационального русского» «общечеловеческой цивилизации» он видел угрозу развития России и её культуры. По его мнению, в мире происходил процесс восхваления именно европейской «общечеловеческой цивилизации», основой для которой служила германо-романская и английская культура (Данилевский, 1995). При этом Н.Я. Данилевский критиковал и славянофилов, чьё учение «если оно напирало на необходимость самобытного национального развития, то отчасти потому, что, сознавая высокое достоинство славянских начал, а также видя успешную уже выказаться в течение долговременного развития односторонность и непримиримое противоречие начал европейских, считало, будто бы славянам суждено разрешить общечеловеческую задачу, чего не могли сделать их предшественники», но в целом «такой задачи... не существует... Задача человечества состоит в проявлении идеи человечества».

Данилевский считал, что «России предстоит сделать выбор: либо вместе с другими славянскими народами создать всеславянскую цивилизацию, либо полностью утратить своё культурно-историческое значение и стать этнографическим материалом для других цивилизаций» (Аксючиц, 2016).

Автор согласен с В.В. Аксютчиц, что «Синтезируя поиски славянофилов и Н.Я. Данилевского, можно сказать, что субъектом исторического действия является не славянский «культурный тип», а русский народ, создавший огромную российскую государственность и сформировавший русскую православную цивилизацию. Таким образом, приоритетом исторического действия для нас является не славянский «культурно-исторический тип», а реальный цивилизационный континент – русская православная цивилизация» (Аксютчиц, 2016).

Владимир Стасов высоко оценил труд Данилевского и вступил в спор с В.С. Соловьёвым, который уже после смерти Данилевского критиковал его труд «Россия и Европа». Данилевский считал, что искусство в России формируется и дает большие надежды на значимое будущее. А Соловьёв утверждал, что великие деятели искусств, такие как Пушкин, Гоголь, Глинка, остались в прошлом и к концу XIX века наблюдается лишь упадок. Стасов же не только признавал, что русские художники «догнали и перегнали» Европу. Русское искусство, «новая русская школа», национальный принцип в искусстве, – подобные доминанты, рассматриваемые как откровение для Запада, как «луч света от России» (по словам Н.А. Бердяева), будут еще долгое время оказывать существенное влияние на всю систему представлений русской художественной интеллигенции» (Луконин, 2010).

Заключение

Философия славянофилов пронизана любовью к России и к её богатейшему историческому и культурному наследию. Многие авторы XIX века признавали, что для развития страны необходимо народное образование. Часто проводили аналогию между образованием и воспитанием, где воспитание должно строиться на уникальности русской культуры и народной духовной традицией. Идеи этнопедагогики органично вплетались в философию славянофилов и многие базировались на них.

В текущем времени, на взгляд автора, необходимо развивать идеи этнопедагогики и включать русскую культуру, народные традиции в современную образовательную систему.

В завершение необходимо поделить цитатой Г.Н. Волкова, который отмечает: «Народ в наиболее чистом виде представляют дети. Когда национальное умирает в детях, то это означает начало смерти нации. При наличии гармонии между национальным и интернациональным чем больше

национального в воспитании, тем сильнее, культурнее, духовно богаче нация» (Волков, 1999).

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Prevention of neurosis in parents of children with disabilities

Abstract:

According to statistics, for every 10,000 healthy children, there are more than 250 children with disabilities in developed countries. Official data of the World Health Organization confirms these figures. In the Russian Federation, 568,000 disabled children were registered in 2013, and by 2020 their number has increased to 688,000. The author examines the main psychological problems of families with children with disabilities, as well as the therapeutic use of methods for preventing neurotic disorders in children. The article analyzes the possibilities of innovative types of neurosis prevention – with the help of psycho-hygiene and psychological cultural studies. The author concludes that disability and concomitant diseases are a powerful stressful factor that forms a complex of experiences, negative psychological deformities in both children and their parents. Deeply correlated psychological complexes actively influence the processes of therapeutic and rehabilitation activities of the child and the adaptation of the family negatively affecting the positive result in every possible way.

Keywords:

prevention of neuroses, modern psychiatry, hygiene, psychological cultural studies.

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Профилактика неврозов у родителей детей с ограниченными возможностями здоровья

Аннотация:

Согласно статистике, на каждые 10 тысяч здоровых детей в развитых странах приходится более 250 детей-инвалидов. Официальные данные Всемирной организации здравоохранения (ВОЗ) подтверждают эти цифры. В Российской Федерации в 2013 году было зарегистрировано 568 тысяч детей-инвалидов, а к 2020 году их число увеличилось до 688 тысяч. Автор рассматривает основные психологические проблемы семей с детьми-

инвалидами, а также терапевтическое применение методов профилактики невротических расстройств у детей. В статье анализируются возможности инновационных видов профилактики неврозов – с помощью психогигиены и психологических культурологических исследований. Автор приходит к выводу, что инвалидность и сопутствующие заболевания являются мощным стрессовым фактором, формирующим комплекс переживаний, негативных психологических деформаций как у детей, так и у их родителей. Глубоко взаимосвязанные психологические комплексы активно влияют на процессы лечебно-реабилитационной деятельности ребенка и адаптации семьи, всячески отрицательно влияя на положительный результат.

Ключевые слова:

профилактика неврозов, современная психиатрия, гигиена, психологическая культурология.

Introduction

According to statistics, for every 10,000 healthy children, there are more than 250 children with disabilities in developed countries. Official data of the *World Health Organization* confirms these figures (The number of disabled people in Russia and the size of the monthly cash payment, 2020).

In the Russian Federation, 568,000 disabled children were registered in 2013, and by 2020 their number has increased to 688,000. The upward trend is obvious (Shats, 2005).

Features of pathologies that caused disability and are defined by disability are directly related to both psychological and pedagogical problems in children and parents, problems that lead to difficulties in psychological adaptation, slowing down the process of socialization, and isolation of the family in society. We have to define the main psychological problems of families with children with disabilities.

1. Regret, sometimes carefully hidden or not realized but indirectly transmitted by parents, falls on the child's guilt. The internal conflict between reality and the desired becomes a difficult test for fathers and mothers.
2. Emotional deprivation of both the child and the parent can be formed if the parent spends their personal resources on the treatment and rehabilitation of the child, while mutual emotional contact either takes a back seat or is completely absent, so both the parent and the child fall into emotional isolation. They cannot express their feelings; they do not have the ability to be mutually acceptable and mutual.
3. The parent's awareness of the anxiety of the future, their child, getting used to the role of the patient, loss of faith in their strength, capabilities and abilities, is

a serious psycho-traumatic factor. As a consequence, the emergence of parental overprotection. As a result, low self-esteem, lack of responsibility for yourself, your own life. A disabled child gets used to the format of existence provided and protected by parents, which does not allow the son or daughter to express themselves.

4. The time factor and shortage of leisure activities. The parent does not have leisure time in their personal space. Therefore, it is not possible to 'reset' the accumulated fatigue and negative energy will be charged with cheerfulness and positive mood. This is only a small part of the psychological problems that lead to the formation of neuroses.

The materials of the study

Modern foreign psychiatry defines neuroses as psychogenic diseases, mostly caused by the influence of objective reality, expressed in various disorders of the mental, physical, and personal plan (Abroze et al., 2017).

It must be recognized that for many years there has been a pathomorphism not only of neuroses as such but also of borderline neuropsychiatric and somatic diseases. In the leaders, neurotic forms with vegetative-visceral disorders, the number of erased, larvated forms of neuropsychiatric and somatic diseases, characterized by a prolonged chronic course and therapeutic resistance, is sharply increasing. In these conditions, disorders of neuro-dynamics by an organic process, secondary neuroticism, and the quality of the individual's response to the underlying disease become unavoidable companions of the pathological process (Ananyev, 2006).

The well-known truth that any disease is easier to prevent than to treat is also very relevant for neuroses. A comprehensive approach to the prevention of neurotic disorders, using multi-faceted methods, gives a positive result. Conditionally, they can be divided into the following areas, based on the professor V.A. Ananyev's *Concept of Health Potentials is a Comprehensive Program for Personal Development*:

1. Emotional sphere. It implies the sensual, creative and spiritual side of the person, which can be realized through creativity in all its manifestations, through various creative spiritual practices, through participation in really socially significant projects.
2. The physical aspect of health. First of all, it means following the principles of a healthy lifestyle, a varied balanced diet, full sleep, sufficient physical activity, and the exclusion of alcoholic beverages and Smoking. Since physical activity plays a significant role in the regulation of homeostasis, it is necessary to discuss them in more detail. Active game sports, primarily team sports and martial arts

were shown to be more effective in compensating for parental burnout.

However, the most important thing of all is to learn to get the maximum emotional pleasure, physical satisfaction from your actions, actions, and feelings, learn 'to catch' the harmony of your personality in all its manifestations and the objectively existing reality of the world around you.

The question often arises: 'Do I need to take a break from my disabled child?' The answer to this question cannot be unambiguous. It is no secret that the attitude of parents to their children is very different. There are examples of both completely irresponsible and unjustified overprotection. A small percentage of adequate parental interaction with the child is somewhere in the middle only. Of course, the disabilities give completely different diseases, but in any case, even if conditionally intact intellect, balanced approach to solving this problem is only correct when the parent not forgetting about their duties objectively assesses own capabilities, the needs of the child, the performance of leisure activities that can bring fatigue, and some related factors, individual to each case separately.

The psycho-hygiene is a special type of the prevention of neurosis. First of all, we are talking about regular visits to a psychotherapist (consultant psychologist). Observing the rule at least two times a year to visit the dentist, many people ignore the visit of another specialist, who is necessary for mental health. Psychological counselling is a form of psychological assistance that establishes a special kind of relationship and/or interaction between the consultant and the client (psychotherapist and patient), which allows you to cope with psychological difficulties, problematic situations, neutralizes the psychological component of psychosomatic disease, or blocks the further development of the disease (Abroze, 2016).

A new science – psychological cultural studies – opens up innovative methods in the prevention of neuroses and psychotherapeutic work. In the modern world, culture as a derivative of human mental activity becomes a multi-faceted, multi-aspect phenomenon based on its inherent branched internal structure and supporting a huge number of functions in society. Many elements of culture are characterized by special mobility in time, responsiveness and accuracy of transmission of features of the period, correlations with the mental processes of society (Abroze et al., 2016). All of them equips the specialist with the rich potential of world culture achievements, which significantly expands preventive methods of working with parents of disabled children.

Conclusion

Thus, disability and concomitant diseases are a powerful stressful factor that forms a complex of experiences, negative psychological deformities in both children and their parents. Deeply correlated psychological complexes actively influence the processes of therapeutic and rehabilitation activities of the child and the adaptation of the family negatively affecting the positive result in every possible way.

Therefore, only a systematic approach to the prevention of neurosis, which is working with the emotional and physical spheres of the individual, regular visits to a psychotherapist (psychologist-consultant) adapt the entire family to the living conditions associated with the child's disability.

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Relevance to define responsibility for decision-making in the documents of strategic development of the Russian Federation's subjects

Abstract:

The article analyzes the theoretical foundations and problems of the formation of the corpus of strategic planning documents in terms of identifying eligible entities as carriers of responsibility for their preparation and execution. Using the example of the Strategy for Economic and Social Development of St Petersburg for the period up to 2035, an attempt is made to determine the scope and subjects of responsibility for making state-type management decisions suitable for implementation at the level of a specific subject within Russia. The authors propose approaches to solving the problems of correctly identifying the subjects of responsibility according to the goals of the strategy for further monitoring and identifying legal violations in the activities of authorities while discussing important political and legal issues of responsibility of public authorities to citizens and the business community.

Keywords:

responsibility, state and municipal structures, decision-making, development strategy, city.

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Государственные решения: управленческие потенциалы и проблемы определения ответственности в документах стратегического развития субъектов Российской Федерации

Аннотация:

В статье проводится анализ теоретических основ и проблем формирования корпуса документов стратегического планирования с точки зрения определения правомочных субъектов в качестве носителей ответственности за их подготовку и исполнение. На примере Стратегии экономического и социального развития Санкт-Петербурга на период до 2035 года реализована попытка определения сферы и субъектов ответственности за принятие управленческих решений государственного типа, пригодных для реализации на уровне специфического субъекта в составе России. Авторы предлагают подходы к решению вопросов корректного определения субъектов ответственности по целям стратегии для дальнейшего контроля и определения правовых нарушений в деятельности органов власти, обсуждая при этом важные политико-правовые вопросы ответственности органов государственной власти перед гражданами и бизнес-сообществом.

Ключевые слова:

ответственность, государственные и муниципальные структуры, управленческие решения, стратегия развития, город.

Introduction

In the Russian management and special legal literature of the current period, this issue is presented and studied, in the opinion of the group of the authors, extremely poorly, especially in terms of analyzing the existence of the fact of responsibility and its presentation in the relevant documentation. In the analysis of a

large number of works dealing with various managerial and legal aspects of responsibility of certain officials and authorities, found the omission appears to be a fairly important issue regarding the presence and determine if the responsibility as such in the framework of the type of the documents, which are fundamental to the development of the country, that relate to the strategic planning documents of federal, regional and municipal levels.

Thus, there is an objective need for an integrated analysis of the political and legal basis to develop and implement the statutory set of documents of strategic development of territories to identify the presence and determine the degree of responsibility of organizations, officials and administrative structures for the management decisions required for technologically competent and legal needs to control the country's strategic planning processes. The higher the level of generalization of plans, programs and projects of strategic development, the more, in the opinion of the group of the authors, the areas of responsibility, its forms and, accordingly, the subjects of responsibility themselves are institutionalized, formalized and partially personified. It should be noted that their presence is the only guarantee of the exhaustive implementation of all parameters and conditions defined by a specific strategic planning document following the requirements of the 172nd Federal Law (Resolution of the Government of St Petersburg of 25.12.2013, no. 1039).

However, it is worth noting that in its essential manifestations, this problem is closely related to a whole complex of not yet fully resolved issues arising from various interpretations of theoretical and methodological and partly philosophical and legal prerequisites that can give an adequate understanding and interpretation of a more general problem of public authorities' participation in the process of initiating and implementing socially significant decisions at different stages of their adoption and implementation.

State authorities, directly or indirectly participating in the process of determining the current agenda, thereby determine the field of possible future, in connection with which any issue of public importance, any potential innovation in public life and any latent conflict can become the subject of discussion, the choice of development options, and therefore political decisions. Representing an integral system of management type, the state power represented by its authors, bodies and institutions, on the one hand, is closed to itself, represents a special environment, in which significant (public and legal) decisions are generally hatched and adopted for implementation. On the other hand, any power is more or less open to its environment, which it tries to command (forcing its subjects to adopt a common

style of life and its reproduction) and to rule (forcing its subjects to act according to the rules defined by the power, accepted at a given time and in a given place).

1.

At different stages of the political process in its managerial dimension, various tasks are set, the general meaning of which is to translate into reality the conceived and adopted decisions of the authorities, developed, as is commonly believed, in the interests of the whole society or some significant part of it. Each country of the modern world has its peculiarities in understanding and organizing these processes. However, there are general laws concerning how each of the branches of state power (and the municipal power that imitates it), as well as each body in a particular branch of government, is invested by its participation in the overall process of state political management. The meaning and purpose of state participation in the process of designing and systematic implementation of state decisions, which are ultimately reduced to a set of legal, regulatory and regulatory (organizing) acts, is to express, record, and clearly present to public opinion the results of their decisive actions by means of approving the right and procedure to represent the interests of a part of society to express, record and clearly present to public opinion the results of their decisive, decisive and resolving (giving the right to legitimate actions) conclusions and ideas about how this or that relevant or important public problem should be overcome or resolved, what means and forces should be used for this, and who on behalf of the state should carry out this activity. It is in this regard that the state and its bodies prove their capacity and solvency in the eyes of society. In cyclic, phasic, rhythmic change of individual phases of the process of passing future state political and administrative decisions as project management and legal activities verified by the organization of the state apparatus and its ability to express the will to have power, which will agree or not agree with the decision-maker or body that is mandated to pursue the case.

The process of development, adoption and implementation of state policy decisions deserves special analysis. The general principles and methodological approaches developed in decision-making theory need a special interpretation to apply to the political sphere and will not work automatically. All stages and regularities of the process of development and decision-making can be present, and, nevertheless, when avoiding the specification of special qualities of the political, the fine line between what is and what is due, the ideal and reality disappear (or in any case is violated). In this case, dialectical balancing in the circle of attraction of various kinds' opposites looks like a burdensome luxury, and imperative generic social

instincts, which are extremely difficult to rationalize, come into play. The solution as an answer to a problematic issue of a vital nature requires a moment of reflection, an analytical-synthetic phase, clarification of the relevance of tendentialities, and Homo Politicus often simply do not have time for such mental actions.

If to begin studying the process of political interactions, then for many, the essence of political action will be reduced to making wise and fair decisions about the current trends in the development of phenomena in the political life of society and offering optimal ways to implement these wise decisions in life (Anderson, 2002). However, if any decisions are made, it means that someone needs it. The reference point of the common good, as well as the unshakable status of the modern interpretation of the human right to a better life, completes this completely rational picture, within which almost any supporter of the ideas of political activism for the sake of freedom gets used to argue. However, for the modern worldview, the activist value-worldview paradigm is clearly not enough, and it must be supplemented by other worldview pictures and approaches to action (and therefore the decision to act), without which political reality is impoverished and deprived of many important nuances. To find an adequate management-power sphere theory of decision-making, the methodology of their development and implementation, as well as methods of calculation and other operations that can take into account not only the costs and benefits but also the subtle plan of human relations and relationships, is still the task of the future, but a considerable number of authors have long been thoroughly and actively engaged in these searches, and some of them (including among political scientists and sociologists) do this quite successfully.

According to S.G. Turonok that it is “the systematic study of public policy (in the form of an analysis of past or evaluation of existing political decisions) with a clear intention to apply the lessons learned to the development of new political initiatives, i.e., taking an applied political character that characterizes political analysis as a scientific discipline.” (Turonok, 2005) To some, this approach may seem too radical, but it seems that the author has fully grasped the essence of political analysis and the core importance for its success of the thematic layer that is set in connection with giving political decision as to the main function of power and the processes associated with it a central place and fundamental importance. It will be much closer to an objective understanding of the political process in all its components if its systematization takes place in connection with the solvability of emerging problems and determination to overcome obstacles to their solutions. A clear advantage of this approach, in the opinion of the group of the authors, is demonstrated by the repeatedly reprinted textbook on the sociology of management

by Z.T. Toshchenko, which is built around just such a thematic core, which allows presenting the processes of political management and power more clearly, and more holistically at the same time (Toshchenko, 2017).

Of course, political analysis is not reducible to factor or characteristic analysis: the qualities of political connections and relations and their quantitative (considered) characteristics, which reflect the basic laws of existence and cognition of the political as the reality of contracts and connections, as well as the general laws of functioning and development of the political sphere of public life, are not formal but stochastic and statistically uncertain. In this regard, the identification of the logical reference point, from which every analytical cycle begins and ends, is extremely necessary, and the political decision as a prototype of political action can well be recognized, in the opinion of the group of the authors, as the initial cell that allows in the process of creating a general theory of political decisions to ascend from the abstractions of political philosophy and ideology to concrete forms of organizing the activities of people, who create their history, among other things, in political terms. Political discourse is essentially a discourse pronounced power ability of the subject to make decisions with knowledge, for the benefit of people and concerning the relief of many variants of adverse developments.

A long history of studying the processes of political governance has allowed us to identify six main phases of the process of solving political problems: initiation, forecasting, legitimation, implementation, evaluation, and termination. Many authors believe that there should be more of these phases. Some of them offer three main ones, indicating the beginning, end, and the process. It is important not only what number of individual phases, into which the process of making and executing political decisions can theoretically be divided, but rather the main turning points, at which a decision made as a conscious act based on rational calculations and prognostic expectations was implemented. Without implementation, the decision remains speculation to reality, virtuality and a good wish, and for the reality of society to be measured in connection with the implementation of the decision, it must be not just 'passing' in political terms but also implemented in practice.

At the same time, a political (and managerial) decision that took place as an act of political guiding, cannot be legally valid in modern conditions if it is incorrectly (in violation of the procedure) formalized and approved if its substantive and formal sides are not in unity, if, finally, the legal form and documentary features are not adequate to the level and position in the political structure. Such a decision, even if made, can be challenged and overturned. However, even if the decision is made following the procedure, agreed with the stakeholders, correlated with the available

opportunities and resources for its implementation, and finally represents the result of a compromise, it may happen that it will not be adequately perceived, adequately interpreted, adequately executed due to failures in the organizational and structural links of the overall management process or direct opposition of interested individuals and groups.

In the phases of preparation, justification and proof of necessity in the decision being made, the initiator tries to prove to himself and others the benefits and advantages of those states of reality that are expected or planned in connection with decision-making. On the implementation phase of the decision more often its initiator is interested in the most complete and adequate to his incarnation, and therefore the monitoring of the actions of the contractor (-s), monitoring the stages of realization of decisions and interference in this process in case of evasion from accepted or regulated by the orders of actions to implement the laid down in the decision in the reality of the subject, social or mental environment is a necessary feature which often is hijacked by government. This is understandable, but it is often not enough. As for the results of the implementation of the adopted political decisions and the assessment of the close and distant (both in space and time) consequences, this phase of the process of making and executing political decisions often falls out of the control of the initiator (this happens because in the process of achieving the goal set by the adopted decision, the idea of what, in fact, this goal consists of, often changes).

This paradox is inherent in any decision-making process, and a political decision differs in this respect mainly in that here, at each phase of its development and execution, extraneous interest and the external influence of actual or potential opposition can interfere. Therefore, as in the process of developing, making and implementing any decision in almost any sphere of human activity to manage the external world of things and objects, as well as the social environment, in the political process of implementing decisions loaded with motivating ideas about the future and achievable, at each of the phases of implementation, repetitions, deviations, iterations and frictions are possible. This is due, in the opinion of the group of the authors, to the cyclical nature of activity and thinking, reflected by the cyclical patterns of organizational and activity functions.

State political administration in the face of relevant persons, bodies and structures is a permanent character of all process of making and implementing political decisions. At each of the above phrases, the presence of state interest is more or less clearly indicated, the expression of this interest is not necessarily related to the explanation of ideological, 'mission' and other motives, but in any case, this

interest takes place. Ultimately, every political decision is a way of asserting power as such. State decisions of a political kind may concern any aspect of the activities of people, their groups and communities, but when taking over (or accepting the functions of the arbiter of fate transferred as a result of agreements or traditions), state bodies and relevant officials only rarely take the initiative to launch the process of design, development and decision-making transferring this right to the upper floors of power. This is due to the peculiarities of the functioning of the state apparatus in its bureaucratic hypostasis: an official of the old bourgeois school (relatively speaking, the first and second generations), in principle, cannot accept the idea of personal initiative and personal responsibility, so the ideal of performance without reasoning is cultivated to this day, even in the conditions of approval of new approaches to public administration and administration.

Even if at some stage, the state authorities give up the initiative in understanding the problem of political significance and its solution by political means, they remain patronizing the process and its results, as well as the quality of participants, stakeholders and experts. In some cases, the direct initiative and primacy of the state and its agents to start activities in connection with the need to make a state political decision is inconvenient or unjustified; in this case, an acceptable option is a kind of reverse delegation of the right to the initiative concerning the processes of finding acceptable solutions (due to the urgent need to remove the contradiction that has matured or has been brought to the conflict phase) to someone from trusted proxies or even completely independent political players who can make explicit and urgently necessary what state institutions should not do based on agreements or as a result of manipulative actions on their behalf and at their own risk. The state will project itself into the reality of society in different ways, and the way of preparing and making fair and reasonable decisions on the key problems of the existence of large masses of people on behalf of and/or on behalf of the highest authorities for this society is one of the most significant ways of reproducing state influence and demonstrating power. The power to rule is the power to decide and at the same time the power to avoid untimely, inappropriate and wrong decisions.

It was noted above that for a socially responsible state, the issue of the legal basis for decisions developed and proposed for the needs of public forces means, in fact, a reflexive (that is, conscious and conscious) position of a political and legal nature, from which it is quite possible (if not necessarily follows) to seek ways to express responsibility for managerial actions that would allow each of those involved in the development and implementation of state decisions to feel like a measure of their involvement in this process, and their measure of responsibility to those social

groups and strata, in the interests of which such decisions, in most cases, are made. However, it should be noted that from the point of view of modern Russian law, not all issues arising here are consistently resolved.

2.

The problems outlined above can be approached in different ways. In this work, the analysis of the presence of responsibility for managerial decision-making is carried out on the example of the *Strategy of Economic and Social Development of St Petersburg for the Period up to 2035* (hereinafter – *the Strategy*), developed based on the resolution of the St Petersburg Government of May 13, 2014, № 355, *On the Strategy of Economic and Social Development of St Petersburg for the Period till 2030* and the proposed for implementation, signed by (then) Georgy Poltavchenko, Acting Governor of St Petersburg (Goncharov, 2013).

This document defines the goals and priorities of the strategic development of all spheres of life of the second largest and most important metropolis of the Russian Federation for the next 17-year period. However, at the time of preparation of this article, this document is not in line with the *Strategy of Spatial Development of the Russian Federation for the Period up to 2025*, adopted based on the decree of the *Government of the Russian Federation*, no. 207-R of February 13, 2019 (Popova, 2011). And the first issue that arises here is: How exactly should an independent subject of the Russian Federation bring the strategic guidelines of its development in line with the decisions of the federal authorities adopted later? Is this a simple correction, or it necessary to agree in advance with the possibility of the radical renovation of the strategic planning document of the subnational level if suddenly there are significant discrepancies with the positions stated in the document of national significance?

Further, according to paragraph 4 of the decree Of the Government of St Petersburg *On the Strategy of Economic and Social Development of St Petersburg for the Period up to 2030*, control over its implementation was entrusted to the Vice-Governor of St Petersburg, and according to paragraph 3, the executive bodies of the city government should be guided by the provisions of *the Strategy* when carrying out their activities. Consequently, the resolution clearly defined one official responsible for the process of evaluating the adequate implementation of *the Strategy* – the Vice-Governor of St Petersburg. It should be noted that this person is not responsible for the implementation of *the Strategy* as a program document but only for monitoring the implementation of the adopted state decision. In other words, the Vice-Governor is never responsible for the implementation of this *Strategy* and the degree of its real implementation in the results of activities. One would assume that the interpretation

of performance monitoring implies the default and the general rule, some personally tied to the figure of the specific officials responsible before the Government and the highest official in St Petersburg, but in the current decision of the *Government of St Petersburg* about the approval of the *Strategy of Social and Economic Development of St Petersburg until 2035* data points defining at least conditionally, subject, recipients and the level of real responsibility for how it, at what pace and with what possible deviations and risks the adopted strategic guidelines will be implemented in the practice of urban life in the megalopolis, are absent. Thus, *the Strategy* adopted by the leadership of the city of federal significance, in fact, has neither a properly defined leader, nor a circle of performers, nor a person responsible for its implementation, and, finally, no one will control the processes of its daily implementation into reality.

In the government decree, there is an indication that the executive bodies in their activities to implement *the Strategy* should be guided by the provisions of this document. Management involves the management of processes for the implementation of certain goals and objectives, organized according to certain rules, placed in the framework of a certain temporary phased planning. The concept of 'management' itself does not contain a clear concept and unambiguously defined content of responsibility for the final result of process management. In the opinion of the group of the authors, this means that if there is a certain discrepancy between plans and results, there are no legal frameworks and definitions of areas and degrees of responsibility that could become a source of actions to correct the situation. Therefore, when determining the degree of discrepancy between the results of process management and the content of planned actions for the implementation of the strategic development priorities and guidelines of a particular area of activity, supervisory authorities can be guided by nothing more than absolute financial and economic indicators, which in most cases, as is known, cannot be correctly identified due to constant current correlations.

It seems that in this case, the necessary subjects, their areas, principles and degree of responsibility should be specifically identified and defined within the framework of *the Strategy*, otherwise, due to the conditionality of the formulation of resolutions and orders of state authorities, the set of management schemes and functions laid down in it will be incomplete. In this regard, the structure of *the Strategy* presented in the annexe to the *Resolution of the Government of St Petersburg* of December 19, 2018, no. 771, needs to be finalized.

Section 2 of the new version of *the Strategy* is devoted to assessing the achieved social and economic goals, while it is assumed that this assessment will be made based on statistical data on the development of St Petersburg following the previously

developed *Strategy for Socio and Economic Development of St Petersburg until 2030* (Goncharov, 2013). It should be noted that the statistical data presented in this section characterize the social and economic state of the urban economy at the end of 2017 and, in fact, are the only basis for further calculations of strategic development indicators for the planned perspective period. Legally, the materials of this section can be interpreted as an absolute zero point of financial and economic calculations, which do not take into account the achieved project indicators for 2018 and the subsequent years allotted for the implementation of *the Strategy*, as well as the intermediate indicators achieved at each step. In the case of incorrect interpretation of data, distortion of the correlation in the direction of increasing or decreasing indicators above or below the economically determined error, which is often found in the calculation formulas of the Ministry of economic development of the Russian Federation, obviously erroneous data may be found at the output. However, the section does not mention the final actual carrier (object) of responsibility, which would form consolidated data for the *Committee on Economic Policy* and strategic development of St Petersburg. Therefore, contrary to what is expected in the current strategic document of the subnational level, at the moment there is a veiled area of responsibility and the subject who should be given this responsibility.

Section 3 of *the Strategy* is on the strategic analysis of competitive advantages of St Petersburg, i.e., combinations of strengths and weaknesses for the social and economic development of the city, which sets the vector to its anticipated motion to desired future states. In the opinion of the group of the authors, the very definition of this section and its content suggests that several entities should be responsible for making managerial decisions on the process of forming such an important analytical material, and first of all, the profile committees of the current government of St Petersburg, headed or controlled by vice-governors. However, the very mention of committees and vice-governors coordinating their activities are also absent in this section. Therefore, legally, such an important component of *the Strategy* as the analysis of the competitive advantages of the city can be carried out in conditions where it is not possible to detect responsible entities identified as responsible public officials since information about this is not indicated or fixed in any special section of *the Strategy*. In the opinion of the group of the authors, it follows from this that after the adoption of *the Strategy* for implementation, no committee of the *Government of St Petersburg* in the event of an unforeseen development of the situation can bear legal or administrative responsibility for the analytical material provided in section 2.

Section 4 reveals a set of scientifically based scenarios for the development of St Petersburg, which makes it actually key since it contains the fundamental settings

for the entire document. However, in this section, there are absolutely no references to any methodology and principles of the chosen method of justifying the development and selection of scenarios. It should be noted that the appeal to science and scientific approaches in Russian society is a kind of guarantee of the quality of decisions made on the management of public affairs. Although the title of the section includes words about scientific justification, no scientific argument in favour of the proposed scenarios can be found in *the Strategy* text. It seems that this is not a fatal but a significant error of the developers of this section. However, more importantly, it seems that it is quite expected that the current strategy does not specify the legal entities or representatives of the scientific community responsible for the development of the scenarios presented in it. Thus, there are grounds to argue that the area of responsibility in the development of scenarios implemented in the context of the implementation of the urban development strategy of St Petersburg is currently not defined either generically (within the framework of a special committee or working group of the *Government of St Petersburg*), or personally (e.g., named developers who proposed the most appropriate methodology for this case and/or performed the development of scenarios).

Section 6 of *the Strategy* defines the priorities, goals and objectives of the social and economic development of St Petersburg in all important vectors from the point of view of desired and expected prospects. In principle, this section is structured quite clearly and definitely and can be quite highly evaluated from the point of view of using its content for political and legal designation of responsibility to make managerial decisions within the framework of *the Strategy* of each subject (carrier) of power and managerial competencies represented by the committees of the *Government of St Petersburg*. In the opinion of the group of the authors, such an approach would help not only to identify but also, so to speak, ‘to zone’, structurally distribute, and label all strategically important areas of city development, as well as in the future, to determine and form a scale to identify the degree of responsibility of everyone who is endowed with this responsibility. However, even in this section, there is no fixation of objects and, therefore, areas of legal responsibility. From the point of view of the law, this means that the priorities of the social and economic development of the city also remain only approximate, not quite clear, and in fact – indicative indicators that can be interpreted differently, and therefore changed at almost any time point of the Strategy implementation, and without additional approval of the entire document as a product of public discussion and consent.

Also, it is necessary to indicate that paragraph 6.2 of section 6 *Directions of Quality Improving of the Urban Environment* is not aligned with the parameters indicated in the

Annex to the order of the *Government of the Russian Federation* dated February 13, 2019, no. 207-R *Strategy of Spatial Development of the Russian Federation for the Period up to 2025*. Even if, e.g., it is considered that this subsection generally corresponds to the national strategy developed after it, then it is necessary at least to make changes to this paragraph, preferably with a special indication of compliance with the document of a higher priority level.

In total, at this stage, *the Strategy* under consideration defines 18 strategic goals of the social and economic policy of St Petersburg, 54 indicators of achievement of the goal and 116 tasks of the city's social and economic policy (Law of St Petersburg no. 771-164). The overall goal of *the Strategy*, as stated in its text, should be determined by four strategic directions:

- 1) human capital development;
- 2) improving the quality of the urban environment;
- 3) ensuring sustainable economic growth;
- 4) ensuring the effectiveness of management and the development of civil society (Law of St Petersburg no. 771-164).

However, the fact that in the current version of the document there is no certainty about the subjects of responsibility for making managerial decisions, neither the area of responsibility nor its degree, although all the goals are clearly outlined and the main strategic directions are defined, inspires some concern. The lack of mention of entities that must implement certain actions to achieve objectives or delegate their execution to the relevant organizers directly management processes, maintaining the highest leadership of sectoral responsibility for implementation of indicators for the future development of the city in the framework of the adopted strategy, can lead to distortion of the direct and inverse relations management, and, therefore, can produce situations of conflict and additional (and currently not explicitly considered) risks.

Section 9 of *the Strategy* defines the terms and stages of its implementation. In the short and medium-term, the goals of *the Strategy* are implemented through state urban programs. The list, which was approved by the decree of the *Government of St Petersburg* from December 25, 2013, no. 1039, *On Procedure of Making Decisions about the Development of State Programs of St Petersburg, Creation, Implementation and Evaluation of Their Effectiveness* (Baturin, 2012), in the current phase of work is exhaustive. However, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that this resolution defines the areas and subjects of responsibility for making managerial decisions but not within the framework of the goals and directions of implementing the Strategy and state programs that already involve the implementation of separate, loosely related goals.

This leads to an absolute dilution of responsibility for making managerial decisions on strategic goals by not quite, in the opinion of the group of the authors, justifiable creation of a kind of ‘multiplicity’ or ‘multiplication’ of responsibility subjects for state programs designed to implement common, but in managerial terms and politically still divided goals. In apparently monotonous and unified approach to identifying the sequence of decision-making and the apparently shared responsibility for the final result of the emerging intersection of the liable entities separate subjects of administrative bodies, committees of the *Government of St Petersburg* and their interest in different methods and mechanisms of state programs as areas of urban development it is possible to imagine a situation inevitably arises in which an unacceptable conflict of interest and, therefore, the law of liability.

Conclusion

Thus, it seems necessary to introduce a rule for the application of a comprehensive analysis of the documents prescribed under the applicable legislation for each type of strategic development of regions, territorial or municipal entities in the Russian Federation to determine the presence and justification of the responsibilities of the state and municipal structures for managerial decision making, defined and lawfully established for this kind of planning. Using the example of *the Strategy* of economic and social development of St Petersburg until 2035, the group of the researches has determined that with increasing generalization of strategic development, the areas of responsibility and, accordingly, the subjects of responsibility require a higher degree and appropriate methods of formalization. This creates legal uncertainty, in which the subjects of responsibility generalized by goals have the opportunity to avoid it and/or shift it to all participants in the process or one of the specific performers of a separate state program. Therefore, among other things, the factor of conditional, formalistic responsibility of the authorities in the person of the relevant Administration’s committees of the Federation’s subject is created, steadily exists and reproduced.

Among the measures that can provide solutions to the problem posed in this article, it is necessary to highlight two, which are proposed to pay special attention to:

- 1) inclusion of a special table with a list of all the goals of the strategy and subjects of responsibility for each of them in the main document of strategic planning of development of each subject of the Federation or supplementary of it, as it was done in St Petersburg, with the corresponding *Implementation Plan* (it should

be noted that the second way is traditional, but, in the opinion of the group of the authors, somewhat outdated);

- 2) availability of the basis for the scientific and legal definition of the markers of the responsibility's boundaries to untimely adopt management decisions, which are necessary to achieve strategic development goals to create opportunities for a clear and unambiguous determination of the fact of legal violation of responsibility in the future.

In the opinion of the group of the authors, this approach will allow, along with other conditions, to ensure greater predictability of actions in the implementation of national strategic projects proposed by the country's leadership and avoid most of the management risks that arise in this process.

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Business process management of retail enterprises based on the process-architectural approach (in Ukrainian)

Annotation:

The acute problems faced by domestic retailers today can be considered: functional specialization, selection of unskilled personnel, including top managers who are poorly versed in process management issues, lack of available automated information systems, low level of detail of business processes, poor quality of information management support. The article includes the process-oriented and architectural approaches to management. The term «enterprise architecture» is the essence and the basic methodologies of enterprise architecture construction are considered. The overall architecture of the enterprise is a combination of business environment architecture and IT architecture. The expediency of introduction of process-architectural approach in the management of retail trade enterprises of substantiated and its advantages are identified. A conceptual model of business process management of retail trade enterprises based on process-architectural approach is proposed.

Keywords:

Management, business processes, process, architectural approaches, process-architectural approach, retail enterprise.

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Управління бізнес-процесами підприємств роздрібної торгівлі на основі процесно-архітектурного підходу

Анотація:

Гострими проблемами, з якими сьогодні стикаються вітчизняні підприємства роздрібної торгівлі, можна вважати: функціональну спеціалізацію, підбір некваліфікованого персоналу,

у тому числі і топ-менеджерів, які слабо розуміються у питання процесного управління, відсутність доступних автоматизованих інформаційних систем, низький рівень діджиталізації бізнес-процесів, низька якість інформаційного забезпечення управління тощо. В статті охарактеризовано процесно-орієнтований і архітектурний підходи до управління. Розкрито сутність терміну «архітектура підприємства» і розглянуто основні методології побудови архітектури підприємства. Відзначено, що загальна архітектура підприємства є поєднання архітектури бізнес-середовища та ІТ-архітектури. Обґрунтовано доцільність впровадження в управління підприємств роздрібної торгівлі процесно-архітектурного підходу та ідентифіковано його переваги. Запропоновано концептуальну модель управління бізнес-процесами підприємств роздрібної торгівлі на засадах процесно-архітектурного підходу.

Ключові слова:

управління, бізнес-процеси, процесний, архітектурний підходи, процесно-архітектурний підхід, підприємство роздрібної торгівлі.

Вступ

Гострими проблемами, з якими сьогодні стикаються вітчизняні підприємства роздрібної торгівлі, можна вважати: функціональну спеціалізацію, підбір некваліфікованого персоналу, у тому числі і топ-менеджерів, які слабо розуміються у питання процесного управління, відсутність доступних автоматизованих інформаційних систем, низький рівень діджиталізації бізнес-процесів, низька якість інформаційного забезпечення управління тощо. Вони суттєво відображаються на результатах діяльності підприємств. Вирішити ці проблеми підприємствам роздрібної торгівлі можливо завдяки імплементації в управління сучасних теорій і концепцій, в арсеналі яких є актуальні, ефективні методи, інструменти, механізми.

В полі зору сучасної управлінської науки є процесно-орієнтований підхід, в межах якого управління спрямовано на бізнес-процеси. Проблемам процесно-орієнтованого підходу присвячено роботи таких вчених, як Б. Андерсен, М. Хамер, Дж. Чампі, Н. Харінгтон, О.М. Криворучко, С.В. Мельниченко, Н.О. Сагалакова. Роздрібна торгівля стала предметом праць Б. Бермана, Дж. Еванса, Л.О. Гелей, С.І. Бая, Л.М. Шимановської-Діанич. Архітектурний підхід, що описує підприємство у якості моделей, розповсюджений в технічних науках і ще не поширений в економічних. Тому виникає необхідність дослідження процесно-архітектурного підходу до управління підприємствами роздрібної торгівлі.

Вищезазначене обумовило визначити предмет, мету і цілі дослідження. Предметом є дослідження теоретичних аспектів процесно-архітектурного підходу до управління підприємствами роздрібною торгівлі. Мета – обґрунтувати доцільності управління бізнес-процесами підприємств роздрібною торгівлі на засадах процесно-архітектурного підходу. Для досягнення мети поставлено наступні цілі:

- охарактеризувати процесно-орієнтований підхід до управління підприємствами;
- визначити концепцію процесно-орієнтовано підходу;
- розкрити сутність архітектурного підходу;
- запропонувати концептуальну модель управління бізнес-процесами підприємства роздрібною торгівлі на засадах процесно-архітектурного підходу.

Дослідження виконано методами: аналізу, синтезу, узагальнення.

Витоки процесно-орієнтованого підходу до управління підприємствами пов'язані зі школами адміністративного менеджменту і наукового управління. Проте, широкого застосування він отримав тільки наприкінці століття. Архітектурний підхід пов'язаний з виникнення і розвитком інформаційних систем. Теоретичні і практичні аспекти цих підходів залишаються на сьогодні науково не вичерпаними.

1. Процесно-орієнтований підхід і його концепція управління підприємствами роздрібною торгівлі

Процесно-орієнтований підхід не нове для управління явище. Але інтенсивний розвиток його теоретико-методологічних засад припав на 1980-х р. Як вказано в п. 2.3.4 ДСТУ ISO 9000:2015 «Системи управління якістю. Основні положення та словник термінів» «...узгоджені та передбачувані результати досягають більш результативно та ефективно, якщо діяльність розуміють та нею керують як взаємопов'язаними процесами, які функціонують як цілісна система» (ДСТУ ISO 9000:2015, 2016). Тобто сутність процесного підходу розкривається через розуміння підприємства як системи процесів. Первинними стають процеси, а не структурні підрозділи підприємства. За цим принципом відбувається й проектування організаційної структури управління, зокрема розподіл функціональних обов'язків. Процесно-орієнтований підхід на відміну від функціонально-орієнтованого також зосереджує увагу на таких

категоріях як результати, цінності, споживачі, постачальники, якість, ресурси тощо.

Провідною концепцією процесно-орієнтованого підходу є управління бізнес-процесами (BPM, Business Process Management), що привернула увагу багатьох теоретиків та практиків. Так, в літературі з управління BPM розглядають як «наукову дисципліну про управління, що спрямована на удосконалення діяльності підприємства шляхом управління його бізнес-процесами»; «як сукупність методів, прийомів та інструментів для виявлення, аналізу, перепроєктування, виконання та контролю бізнес-процесів» (Джестон та Неліс, 2015; Dumas та ін., 2018).

Варто підкреслити, що, BPM не єдина концепція, що присвячена вдосконаленню діяльності. На ряду з нею існують Загальний менеджмент якості (TQM), операційний менеджмент, «Шість сігм», «заощадливе виробництво», Kaizen. На відміну від зазначених концепцій, BPM спрямовує зусилля на бізнес-процеси як фундамент діяльності підприємств. За логікою концепції якість – тільки один із можливих критеріїв оцінювання і удосконалення бізнес-процесів, і, як похідних, їх результатів. В межах концепції управління бізнес-процесами вдало поєднуються положення класичного менеджменту, менеджменту якості, а також досягнення науково-технічного прогресу – інформаційні технології. Це робить управління підприємствами всебічним, інтерактивним, комплексним.

Враховуючи вищевизначені визначення BPM, спробуємо визначити його основні напрямки. До них належать:

- 1) виділення та проєктування бізнес-процесів;
- 2) методичне забезпечення впливу на бізнес-процеси;
- 3) реалізація бізнес-процесів;
- 4) аналіз, оцінювання, контроль бізнес-процесів;
- 5) удосконалення (оптимізація) бізнес-процесів.

Таким чином, встановлено, що ідеї процесно-орієнтованого підходу виникли наприкінці XIX ст. Однак, своєї популярності він отримав тільки у XX ст. Його сутність і положення визначені і стандартах ISO. Управління бізнес-процесами BPM – провідна концепція процесно-орієнтованого підходу, яка, на відміну від концепцій Загального менеджменту якості, поєднує удосконалення бізнес-процесів і використання інформаційних технологій.

2. Управління бізнес-процесами підприємств роздрібної торгівлі на основі процесно-архітектурного підходу

Побудова процесно-орієнтованого підприємства на інформаційних засадах для багатьох вітчизняних суб'єктів господарювання залишається невиконаним завданням. Це можна пов'язати з тим, що керівники не розуміються як переформувати діяльність підприємств і створити архітектуру на основі бізнес-процесів, узгоджуючи їх з інформаційними технологіями. З метою вирішення цієї проблеми пропонуємо розглянути архітектурний підхід і доповнити ним процесно-орієнтований підхід.

Перш ніж поглинути у дослідження архітектурного підходу необхідно з'ясувати сутність терміну «архітектура підприємства», що є його основою.

Вперше термін «бізнес-архітектура» почав використовуватися в наукових колах завдяки розробникам методології TOGAF (The Open Group Architecture Framework). Однак, ця методологія не єдина, що визначає архітектуру підприємства. Так, у міжнародному стандарті ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2011 «Systems and software engineering – Architecture description» архітектура тлумачиться як фундаментальні концепції або властивості системи в її оточуючому середовищі, втілені в її елементах, зв'язках і принципах проектування та еволюції системи (ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2011). Треба відмітити, що в стандарті дано абстрактне визначення архітектури. Це може призвести до виникнення проблем, пов'язаних із практичною побудовою архітектури підприємства. Оскільки не зрозуміло які саме втілені концепції і властивості системи.

Архітектура підприємства – це модель всіх його ключових елементів і зв'язків між ними (включаючи бізнес-процеси, технології, інформаційні системи), а також процес підтримки змін бізнес-процесів зі сторони інформаційних технологій (Краснов та Диязитдинова, 2012). У цьому визначенні акцентується увага на структурі архітектури, що може бути використана при її візуалізації.

Іншими словами архітектура підприємства – комплексне уявлення про підприємство, що відображає його структури, оточення, зв'язки і інформаційні системи підтримки. Архітектуру можна представити у наочно у вигляді моделі.

На сьогоднішній день можна виокремити декілька методологій побудови архітектури підприємств на базі інформаційних технологій. До них належать:

- 1) Zachman Framework for Enterprise Architecture (ZIFA);
- 2) The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF);
- 3) Federal Enterprise Architecture Framework (FEAF);
- 4) Gartner Enterprise Architecture.

Модель Захмана (ZIFA) – це каркас архітектури підприємства. Включає п'ять артефактів, а саме «Дані», «Функція», «Мережа», «Люди», «Час», «Мотивація» (Альшанская та Хрипунов, 2017). Система підприємства описується з точки зору основних суб'єктів та артефактів, інформація про які заноситься в таблицю. По вертикалі визначаються ключові суб'єкти, які отримують інформацію про артефакти; по горизонталі – самі артефакти. Зацікавленими особами є, наприклад, керівник підприємства, бізнес-аналітик тощо. Беручи до уваги простоту побудови цієї моделі, до недоліків можна віднести її слабу фіксованість. Оскільки через переміщення або відсутність хоча б однієї позиції втрачаються всі дані про неї. Це може призвести до плутанини і помилок в управлінських рішеннях.

The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF) належить концерну The Open Group. До її складу належать наступні категорії:

- 1) архітектура бізнес-процесів – описує всі групи бізнес-процесів;
- 2) архітектура додатків – описує перелік програм, що використовує підприємство, а також взаємозв'язки між ними;
- 3) архітектура даних – описує сховища даних і процедури доступу до них;
- 4) архітектура технологій – описує інфраструктуру обладнання та програмного забезпечення, у якому запускаються і взаємодіють додатки (Альшанская та Хрипунов, 2017).

Дана методологія є логічним продовженням моделі Захмана, оскільки встановлює артефакти та зацікавлених в них осіб. TOGAF, по-перше, є моделлю архітектури підприємства. По-друге, завдяки компоненту ADM є методикою побудови архітектури, що утворює певний континуум підприємства. Доречно підкреслити, що методологія TOGAF формує архітектуру різних спеціалізацій завдяки наявній технічній еталонній моделі TRM та інформаційним стандартам SIB. Так, фундаментальна є універсальною і може використовуватися в практиці будь-яких підприємств. Загальносистемна є більш специфічною, однак використовується в діяльності багатьох однорідних підприємств. Галузева притаманна конкретній сфері господарювання. Як приклад, в торговельній галузі може використовуватися підприємствами будь-яких спеціалізацій і форматів. Для конкретного підприємства в межах TOGAF розробляється індивідуальна архітектура.

Далі охарактеризуємо архітектуру федеральної організації (FEAF), що була запропонована Урядом США у 2006 р. (Альшанская та Хрипунов, 2017). Ця методологія поєднує таксономію Захмана і процес побудови архітектури, описаний в TOGAF. Методологія FEAF містить п'ять еталонних моделей:

«модель бізнесу», «модель обслуговування», «модель компонентів», «технологічна модель», «модель даних». FEAF дозволяє узгодити між собою різні компоненти підприємства (п'ять моделей), підсилити взаємодію між ними, визначити проблеми кожної і розробити заходи їх усунення. Вона є комплексною і змістовною. Проте, на сьогоднішній день не є поширеною і практично апробованою підприємствами.

Методологія Gartner – набір загальних рекомендацій щодо побудови архітектури, що були розроблені консалтинговими компаніями. Основною ідеєю є те, що стратегія первина по відношенню до архітектури. Тобто вона визначає напрямок діяльності підприємства, його майбутні результати. Методологія Gartner на відміну від вищерозглянутих методологій не містить алгоритму розробки архітектури. Послідовність розробки, впровадження архітектури, вимоги до неї встановлюються відповідальними за цей процес особами і погоджуються топ-менеджментом підприємств.

Розглянуті методології мають певні переваги та недоліки. Вибір тієї чи іншої методології залежить від потреб і проблем конкретного підприємства в певний період часу. Однак, всі вони описують:

- 1) архітектуру бізнес-середовища;
- 2) архітектуру інформаційних технологій.

Архітектура бізнес-середовища пов'язана з визначенням місії, стратегій, середовищем, формуванням організаційної структури, ідентифікацією бізнес-процесів, посадових осіб, інформаційних і матеріальних потоків. Ідентифікація бізнес-процесів найчастіше відбувається за наскрізним принципом, так і за комплексним, коли визначаються весь набір бізнес-процесів. Архітектура інформаційних технологій представлена архітектурою інформаційних систем, архітектурою даних, архітектурою технологій.

Таким чином, в даному дослідженні рекомендується управляти підприємствами роздрібною торгівлі на засадах процесно-архітектурного підходу. Сутність якого полягає в тому, що для досягнення високого рівня ефективності діяльності підприємства необхідно створити систему бізнес-процесів і поєднати її з системою інформаційних технологій. Використання інформаційних технологій є обов'язковою умовою для підприємств роздрібною торгівлі в умовах діджиталізації.

Беручи до уваги вищерозглянуте, пропонуємо авторську концептуальну модель управління бізнес-процесами підприємств роздрібною торгівлі на засадах процесно-архітектурного підходу (іл. 1.).

Управління бізнес-процесами підприємств роздрібною торгівлі на процесно-архітектурних засадах має наступні переваги:

- 1) формування моделі підприємства і визначення її складових;
- 2) розгляд підприємства як цілісного утворення, що поєднує архітектуру бізнес-середовища і архітектуру інформаційних технологій;
- 3) керування бізнес-процесами на основі ІТ: моделювання, моніторинг, вдосконалювання;
- 4) автоматизація і діджиталізація бізнес-процесів;
- 5) базування на принципах сучасності, надійності, якості, динамічності, системності;
- 6) створення еталонних моделей архітектури, що використовуються для управління всіма об'єктами (одиницями) мережі підприємства роздрібною торгівлі;
- 7) керування архітектурою як процесом, який аналізується, оцінюється, вдосконалюється;
- 8) співпраця і взаємодія між структурними підрозділами;
- 9) ліквідація розривів між бізнес-архітектурою і ІТ-архітектурою;
- 10) створення єдиної корпоративної системи задля управління бізнесом та інформаційними потоками;
- 11) розгляд підприємства з точки зору керівників, відповідальних за бізнес-процеси і ІТ-спеціалістів;
- 12) створення реальної («як є») і майбутньої («як має бути») моделей архітектури підприємства.

Таким чином, в умовах діджиталізації підприємствам роздрібною торгівлі доцільно управляти на основі процесно-архітектурного підходу, що поєднує бізнес-процеси, інформаційні системи і технології.

Висновок

Таким чином, в статті розкрито сутність процесно-орієнтованого і архітектурного підходів до управління підприємствами. Встановлено, що загальним для них є використання в управлінській діяльності інформаційних технологій. Однак, саме процесно-архітектурний підхід дозволяє візуалізувати ключові елементи (архітектуру бізнес-середовища і ІТ-архітектуру), їх зв'язки і поєднати все це у єдине ціле у якості загальної архітектури підприємства. В межах цього підходу побудова архітектури може бути виконана завдяки методологіям ZIFA, TOGAF, FEAF, Garter. Аналіз наукової літератури

дозволив виділити основні переваги процесно-архітектурного підходу і запропонувати його концептуальну модель, що повинна реалізувати основну мету управління бізнес-процесами роздрібною торгівлі – підтримання стійкості підприємства і досягнення конкурентоспроможності і довгострокової перспективи.

Можна констатувати факт, що мету і завдання дослідження було досягнуто. Подальше дослідження буде спрямоване на огляд методичного забезпечення управління бізнес-процесами підприємств роздрібною торгівлі.

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Додаток

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